
**Deliverable – Report on
output-based surveillance
system selection
methodology ¹**

OHEJP JIP MATRIX – WP3

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WP3 – TASK 3: SELECTION OF APPROPRIATE OUTPUT-BASED SURVEILLANCE SYSTEMS

Introduction

The One Health European Joint Project (OHEJP) MATRIX aims to build on existing resources within One Health Surveillance by creating synergies along the whole surveillance pathway including the animal health, human health and food safety sectors. The concept of One Health (OH) promotes the decompartmentalisation of human, animal, and ecosystem health for more efficient and sustainable governance of complex health issues (Bordier *et al.*, 2020). However, many surveillance databases have evolved from the different requirements of the different sectors (Houe *et al.*, 2019), for instance, ongoing active/passive surveillance for pathogens in the animal sector and outbreak data in the human sector (Comin *et al.*, 2019) which makes it difficult to co-ordinate a OH approach. Output based standards (OBS) can allow for variation in surveillance activities to achieve the same objective and may be useful in the OH context where surveillance for animal pathogens can act as risk indicators for human health. Although, this may not always be possible if there is no correlation between the presence of the pathogen in the animal sector and food safety/human health. Animal health surveillance includes animal conditions which may pose a threat to human health – either directly or via food products – even where such conditions are unapparent in the animal itself (Drewe *et al.*, 2012).

Traditional methods of defining surveillance activities have been historically based on stipulating the number of samples to be taken e.g. sampling 10 out every 100 batches or 50% of batches. Using this approach, different systems can easily demonstrate equivalence but, using the same example, it assumes that every batch entering a process poses exactly the same risk. This might not always be the case, however, with different batches presenting different risks and this introduces a complication when comparing the results from different surveillance systems. Similarly, the heterogeneity of control and surveillance programmes that are designed and implemented based on country specific conditions renders it difficult to compare probabilities of freedom from infection estimated from collected surveillance data. To address this, OBS have been proposed as an approach to enable direct comparison of non-standard surveillance systems. Rather than prescribing exactly what sampling must be applied, an OBS describes what a surveillance system must achieve in measurable units e.g. surveillance sensitivity or confidence in probability of freedom if a disease is absent or case finding capacity if a disease is present (Cameron 2012). Using OBS therefore allows for the application of different surveillance systems which are relevant to a region/country's specific situation. Such systems may vary in their methodologies, the choice of which can be influenced by a variety of factors including disease prevalence, performance of the tests used, risk factors of infection, structure of the surveillance programme and frequency of testing. A specified OBS allows for a comparable standard to be achieved as the comparison of surveillance outputs from heterogeneous surveillance programmes can be a difficult task (Meletis *et al.*, 2022).

Output based standards thus allow for variation in surveillance activities based on, for example: risk-based sampling, the choice of alternative sampling and testing methods or combination of different surveillance components, provided these are agreed between the relevant stakeholders. Demonstrating a statistically based confidence in the outcome e.g. the probability of disease being below a specified design prevalence given the number of test results can be a powerful output providing proof of official disease free status which can guarantee access to international trade. However, although the current legislative framework exists for countries to take an OBS approach to surveillance, previous work within the RISKSUR project identified that few countries are implementing this approach (Peyre *et al.*, 2019). Most surveillance, control and monitoring programmes still rely on input-based standards instead.

Key to the effectiveness of any surveillance system is the selection of appropriate methodologies to achieve the objectives of the system. The objective of the project MATRIX² WP3³ is to develop guidelines for the design, implementation, and evaluation of official controls within the food sector using OBS by looking at the practicalities of implementing output-based surveillance within a OH context. While the focus is on OH activities, it may be that there are situations where specific industry focused efforts are most effective and efficient with regard to OBS. For instance, many pathogen control programmes are based on the principle of bottom-up eradication i.e. controlling disease at the animal level to curtail disease at the public health level.

For this WP3 objective, each of the partners involved have selected a surveillance pathogen that is relevant to their specific situation:

- *Salmonella* Dublin in cattle (Denmark) (pg. 5)
- *Salmonella* in layer flocks (European Union/United Kingdom) (pg. 20)
- *Salmonella* in pigs (Sweden) (pg. 27)
- *Echinococcus multilocularis* risk populations (Poland) (pg. 33)
- *Echinococcus multilocularis* testing (Great Britain) (pg. 38)
- Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-COV-2) (the Netherlands) (pg. 43)

Partners have then conducted a case study relevant to the hazard which describes either a specific component or a method that is applicable to the objective of achieving an OBS within a OH context. These case studies are presented in this document to be used as examples of data, methods or components which may need to be considered prior to establishing an OBS surveillance programme depending on the specific hazard and situation.

² MATRIX is a project of the [One Health European Joint Programme \(OHEJP\)](#), a partnership of 44 food, veterinary and medical laboratories and institutes across Europe and the [Med-Vet-Net Association](#). MATRIX connects existing cross-sectorial One Health programmes in European countries. Today, 19 partner institutes representing the animal health, public health and food safety sectors from 12 countries continue a collaboration that started early in 2020 and will end in December 2022. More information can be found [here](#).

³ This document is a product of Work Package 3 in the MATRIX project. Contributors to that WP are the OHEJP partners 21-APHA, 34-PIWET, 41-SVA, UCPH, 31-WBVR, 33-NVI and 28-IZSAM.

Case studies

1. Case study 1 – *Salmonella* Dublin in cattle

1.1. *Salmonella* Dublin in Denmark

Beate Conrady, Liza Rosenbaum Nielsen, Hans Houe (UCPH)

(*Table and figure numbers are consecutive for this case study only)

1.2. Introduction

Salmonella enterica subspecies *enterica* serovar Dublin (*Salmonella* Dublin) is a host-adapted bacterium known to have an impact on productivity and welfare in infected cattle herds. Importantly, the organism also has zoonotic potential and is characterised by a more invasive disease and a higher mortality in people than other non-typhoidal *Salmonella* serovars (Lester *et al.*, 1995; Helms *et al.*, 2003). There is evidence of seasonality in *S. Dublin* infection, with an increase in diagnoses during the autumn season. Carrier cattle may shed the bacterium constantly, intermittently or may become a latent carrier i.e. those that temporarily shed the bacteria in faeces, becoming infective to naïve animals. This shedding is often associated with periods of stress in latent carriers e.g. around calving. Active carriers will also shed in higher numbers around periods of stress. Zoonotic infections may be acquired by direct contact with cattle or faecal matter, or through ingesting unpasteurised milk products (Henderson *et al.*, 2017).

1.3. Background information on *S. Dublin* in Denmark*

* The following description gives a short overview because the *S. Dublin* programme is updated every year, especially with regard to restrictions, mandatory actions, and follow-up sampling in Level 2 herds. For instance, there was a level 3 for salmonellosis and culture-positive herds, but these are today currently in Level 2. Further, there is no longer special hygienic slaughter unless there is salmonellosis in the herd including clinical signs caused by any *Salmonella* species not only *S. Dublin*.

On average, 20 people per year in Denmark get infected with *S. Dublin* such as through contaminated food (SSI, 2022) though the number of infections is likely underreported. To increase animal and public health by reducing welfare losses, economic losses in infected herds and the number of human cases, there is a national surveillance and control programme in place regularly testing and classifying all cattle herds for signs of *S. Dublin* infection in Denmark. *Salmonella* Dublin is notifiable meaning that owners of animals with a suspicion of salmonellosis must call a veterinarian to confirm or reject the diagnosis and laboratories that isolate *Salmonella* have to report the results to the veterinary authorities (Houe *et al.*, 2019).

The following diagnostic methods are available to detect *S. Dublin*:

- 1) Live bacteria (e.g. in faeces, organ tissues, fluids or environmental samples) by using conventional bacteriological culture methods
- 2) PCR (same types of samples as 1)
- 3) Antibodies (e.g. in blood and milk) by using indirect O-antigen-based ELISA (Nielsen, 2013)

To determine whether animals have been exposed to *S. Dublin*, bulk-tank milk (BTM) samples in dairy herds are tested four times per year. In non-dairy herds, with 10 animals or more, blood samples are collected at slaughter over time through an automatic IT-system selecting animals for slaughter to be analyzed serologically; the status of the herd is based on the last 8 blood samples (Nielsen, 2013). Farmers can also request extra BTM or blood samples, if they want to know more or confirm their test-status. If a herd becomes test-positive (indicative of *S. Dublin* infection according to specified criteria), special requirements to prevent the spread of the infection within and between farms will be introduced.

For instance, herds will be put under official veterinary supervision by veterinary authorities and strict animal movement restrictions will be put in place. In case clinical salmonellosis is present in the farm, animals can only be sent for special hygienic slaughter. Despite all control efforts, an increase in the number of infected farms has been observed over the last couple of years. At the beginning of 2022, 11.2% of dairy herds were not found test-negative for *S. Dublin* and the year before it was 9.8% (not in Level 1; see description of the levels below). The majority of the test-positive dairy herds are located in specific regions of Denmark: Jylland-Syd, Jylland-Sydvest, Himmerland, Jylland-Midtvest and Jylland-Midt (SEGES, 2022).

Cattle herds have been assigned into three levels since 2002:

- Level 3: Salmonellosis and culture positive (until 2021)
- Level 2: Test-positive (or not able to be placed in Level 1)
- Level 1: Test-negative according to given test-criteria in the legislative order

In total, four BTM antibody tests are performed per year, and the farmer does not know when or which BTM samples will be used for the *S. Dublin* enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) analyses. Every third (from 2011 every fourth) month, BTM samples from all dairy farms are tested in the national surveillance programmes for *S. Dublin*. The classification of herds into Level 1 is based on the average ELISA optical density coefficient (ODC%) value of four consecutive BTM samples, and the ODC% in the most recent sample compared to the average of the previous three (Nielsen, 2013; Nielsen, 2021).

Two criteria to remain in Level 1:

- The average of the last 4 BTM-samples must be below 25 ODC%
- The ODC%-value of the most recent BTM-sample must not be more than 20 higher than the average of the previous 3 samples ('the jump criteria').

BTM only includes measurements on lactating cows producing milk to the tank for delivery to the dairy company. Hence, it does not provide indications about infection in young stock and non-dairy herds. Thus, for non-dairy herds, in total 8 antibody tests on blood samples are taken and all samples have to be below 50 ODC% to remain in Level 1. The newest legislation furthermore requires a strict blood sampling scheme in calves and young stock in Level 2 to document effect of control measures. Hence, herds must be test-negative in both young stock and BTM before they can be moved to Level 1. Table 1 provides an overview of the cattle herd classification.

Table 1: Overview of the Danish *S. Dublin* herd classification programme (as of 10th of March 2022)

Official surveillance levels	Official interpretation	Criteria	Consequences dictated by legislation
Level 1	Most likely free from <i>S. Dublin</i>	<p><i>Dairy herds:</i> Average ODC% < 25 in the last four BTM samples and the last sample not increased > 20 ODC% compared to the average of the previous 3 samples.</p> <p><i>Heifer-raising facilities receiving cattle from one other property:</i> 8 blood samples once per year all below 50 ODC%.</p> <p><i>Heifer-raising facilities receiving cattle from two or more other properties:</i> 8 blood samples twice per year (with 5-8 month interval) all below 50 ODC%.</p>	None (except that these herds cannot buy cattle from herds in Level 2).

Official surveillance levels	Official interpretation	Criteria	Consequences dictated by legislation
		<i>Other non-dairy herds:</i> The last 8 blood samples (typically collected at abattoirs) tested all below 50 ODC%.	
Level 2	Possibly infected with <i>S. Dublin</i> , based on too high antibody levels (or not living up to Level 1-criteria)	Does not live up to the test-criteria for Level 1 or may have had risky contacts detected.	Herds put under official veterinary supervision. Cannot move cattle for live trade, only directly to slaughter. Can only export calves, not sell calves for fattening in Denmark. Have to make a written action plan with local veterinarian and will be visited by veterinary authorities checking the action plan and documentation for effect thereof. Have to test calves according to sample size calculation based on herd size four times per year, and young stock above 6 months old twice per year also according to sample size calculation. Must be test-negative in calves, young stock and BTM before being able to move to Level 1.

1.4. Deliverable 1

A description of publicly available data regarding *S. Dublin* related to output-based surveillance programmes in Denmark.

In total, there are eight public domain datasets available regarding *S. Dublin* for cattle herds and public domain data regarding *S. Dublin* infections in humans. The *S. Dublin* level of each cattle property in Denmark is publicly available through the Central Husbandry Register (CHR: <https://chr.fvst.dk/>) (Screenshot in Figure 1). By entering the respective individual farm holdings number (CHR; Hvad in Danish) in the search mask (Figure 1), anyone can view the current *S. Dublin* status of the cattle property with the associated date of the *S. Dublin* level assignment (see red circle in Figure 1).

Landbrug og Fiskeri
Fødevarestyrelsen

Centrale Husdybrugsregister - CHR

Forside | Om CHR | Kontakt

Ejendomme | **Besætninger** | Aquafarms | Leveringserklæringer | Kvæg | Kvægpas | Besætningsliste | Flytteliste | Flytningsdokument

Find besætning

Hvad: Medtag ophørte besætninger

eller

Hvem: Vælg evt. dyreart

Hvor: Vælg evt. besætningstype

Fandt 1 besætning

CHR nr.	Besætningsnr.	Besætningstype	Må dyr omsættes	Ophørt	Dyr i alt
100000	100000	Malkekvægsbesætning	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nej	657

Ejer
Aarhus Universitet
Nordre Ringgade 1
8000 Aarhus C

Bruger
Aarhus Universitet
Nordre Ringgade 1
8000 Aarhus C

Ejendom
CHR nr.: 100000
Burrehøjvej 49
Foulum
8830 Tjele
[Vis besætninger](#)
[Vis på kort](#)

Størrelse
Handyr: 54
Kvier: 321
Køer: 282
Ajourført: 07. jan. 2022

Besætningsoplysninger
Veterinære problemer: Nej
Ejers oplysning om fødevarekædeoplysninger OK: Ja
Salmonella Dublin niveau: Niveau 1 siden 04-02-2006

Dyrlægepraksis
Praksisnr.: 3514
Dr. Vammen Dyrlæge
Vestergade 6,ST
Foulum
8830 Tjele

Figure 1: The S. Dublin levels of the cattle herds were made publicly available on the internet. N.B. Searching based on individual CHR Farm Registration Number.
Source 1: <https://chr.fvst.dk/chri/faces/chri>

To collect all S. Dublin status data of approximately 15,000 cattle farms (n=2,400 dairy herds and 12,500 non-dairy herds) in Denmark, the prerequisite is that the CHR number of each cattle farm is known. All cattle farms with their associated S. Dublin Status are mapped for all of Denmark in a publicly available map (Figure 2).

This page is part of [KvaegVet.dk](http://kvaegvet.dk)

As of July 2009, this map shows the official Salmonella Dublin levels.

Figure 2: Distribution of cattle herd classification stratified by S. Dublin level ('Niveau') and regions (state of: 05.01.2022) Source 2: <http://www.kvaegvet.dk/>

Further, S. Dublin BTM and blood test results for dairy and non-dairy herds are publicly available in aggregated form for different periods. The properties of "non-free" cattle herds i.e. not assigned into S. Dublin Level 1 are shown in Figure 3. The "Antibodies" column shows the proportion of cattle properties that have too high antibody level in their samples (see detailed description in Table 1). The difference in the numbers of the two columns can be partly explained due to properties that are allocated in Level 2 (in Danish 'Niveau 2') caused by risky contacts with infected farms or that dairy properties obtain their official level from coincidental or preshow blood testing (see further description: <http://www.kvaegvet.dk/>). Therefore, the percentage for "non-Free" can vary from the percentage shown for "antibodies" in Figure 3.

Date (Last date is at the top)	Properties with special slaughter	Non-dairy properties		Dairy properties	
		Non-free	Antibodies	Non-free	Antibodies
05-01-2022		12574 properties		2444 properties	
05-01-2022	0	2.4%	2.3%	11.2%	9.9%
01-12-2021	0	2.2%	2.3%	10.6%	9.5%
03-11-2021	0	2.2%	2.3%	10.4%	9.6%
06-10-2021	0	2.1%	2.2%	10.3%	9.4%
01-09-2021	0	2.1%	2.2%	9.4%	8.7%
04-08-2021	0	2.0%	2.2%	9.3%	8.7%
07-07-2021	0	2.1%	2.3%	9.0%	8.7%
02-06-2021	9	2.1%	2.3%	9.1%	8.5%
05-05-2021	10	2.2%	2.3%	9.2%	8.8%
07-04-2021	14	2.2%	2.4%	9.6%	8.9%
03-03-2021	7	2.4%	2.4%	9.5%	8.8%
03-02-2021	8	2.4%	2.4%	9.9%	9.3%
06-01-2021	15	2.3%	2.5%	9.8%	9.4%
02-12-2020	12	2.4%	2.5%	9.5%	8.9%
04-11-2020	10	2.4%	2.6%	9.0%	8.2%
07-10-2020	6	2.3%	2.5%	9.3%	8.2%
02-09-2020	8	2.2%	2.6%	8.2%	7.6%
05-08-2020	8	2.2%	2.4%	8.1%	7.6%
01-07-2020	7	2.3%	2.4%	8.5%	7.7%
03-06-2020	9	2.3%	2.4%	8.3%	7.7%
06-05-2020	8	2.6%	2.5%	8.9%	8.1%
01-04-2020	9	2.5%	2.5%	9.2%	8.6%
04-03-2020	11	2.8%	2.6%	9.4%	8.6%
05-02-2020	10	2.8%	2.7%	9.4%	8.9%

Figure 3: *Salmonella* Dublin bulk milk and blood test results in the period e.g. from 05.02.2020-05.01.2022 for dairy and non-dairy herds. N.B. The figures in the column "Non-free" show the proportion of properties that do not have official Level 1. Source 3: <http://www.kvaegvet.dk/>

In contrast to Figure 2 where the *S. Dublin* level is visible per cattle property (Figure 1 and 2) the laboratory antibody test results of BTM and blood samples per cattle herd are not public available (Figure 3 and 4). The number of properties in the *S. Dublin* levels for non-dairy and dairy herds stratified by Level 1 and 2 is public domain as well (Figure 4).

Number of properties in <i>Salmonella</i> Dublin levels	Non-dairy properties	Dairy properties
1, probably Dublin free	12275	2171
2, due to antibodies	145	219
2, due to trade / contact	103	27
2, other matters	33	27
Unknown level	18	0
Total	12574	2444
Key figures:		
Not free properties	2.4%	11.2%
of which at unknown level	0.1%	0.0%
In all with special slaughter	0	

Note that in this statement, no co-operation has been taken into account, just as the definition of 'milk supplier' in this statement may in some cases deviate from the official definition thereof. This is the explanation for the fact that in this statement there may be non-milk delivery properties listed under level 1a and milk delivery properties under 'Unknown'.

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Figure 4: Overview of *Salmonella* Dublin Levels (state of: 05.01.2022) Source 4: <http://www.kvaegvet.dk/>

The distribution of dairy herds in S. Dublin level 2 and 3 stratified by region and period are public domain and shown in Figure 5 (note that Level 3 does not exist in the newest legislative order from 2021 but has not yet been removed from the figure display).

Below, milk suppliers are divided according to the [Salmonella regions](#) that have been established in 2008.

A milk supplier in this inventory is a property from which a Salmonella Dublin milk sample has been available within the last 5 months.

Region	Milk suppliers		
	Total number	Numbers in levels 2 and 3	Percentage in levels 2 and 3
Bornholm	23	1	4.3%
Zealand	107	3	2.8%
Fyn	139	0	0.0%
Jutland - South	572	112	19.6%
Jutland - Southwest	238	52	21.8%
Jutland - Midwest	378	31	8.2%
Jutland - East	177	1	0.6%
Jutland - Central	264	21	8.0%
Himmerland	280	46	16.4%
Jutland - North	319	11	3.4%
The whole country	2497	278	11.1%

Figure 5: Distribution of dairy herd classification stratified by S. Dublin Level and region (state of: 05.01.2022) N.B. Milk suppliers are divided according to the Salmonella regions that have been established in 2008. A dairy herd in this inventory is a property from which a S. Dublin milk sample has been available within the last 5 months. The solid black line in the figure is the national average percentage of dairy cattle properties in Level 2 (and previously also Level 3) over time in the surveillance programme. Source 5: <http://www.kvaegvet.dk/>

Milk suppliers are divided according to the same geographical regions that were defined in 2008 to provide an overview. Antibody levels of dairy herds stratified in more detail by geographical regions are shown in Figure 6.

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Figure 6: Distribution of non-dairy cattle herd classification stratified by S. Dublin Level and regions (as of 5th January 2022)

The distribution of properties of non-dairy herds of S. Dublin Level 2 and 3 stratified by slaughter calf, beef cattle, cattle herds with a high number of heifers and age groups as well as over the periods is shown in Figure 7 (including definition of the non-dairy herd classification). N.B. The terms “old animals”, “annuals” and “yearling” refer to “year animal” which corresponds to one animal on the property for a whole year or. e.g. two animals for half a year each. For instance, “over 30 year old animals means “30 year animals (see Figure 7)”.

Categorization of non-milk delivery properties in connection with Salmonella-Dublin

The focus is on describing these different groups of properties:

- Properties with a high proportion of heifers (primarily heifer hotels)
- Properties with calves for slaughter
- Properties with beef cattle
- Other properties

None of these groups are clear to designate from database information, but we can at our discretion try. For resp. slaughter calves, beef cattle and others are worked with two groups, depending on the number of animals.

The following definitions are used:

Group	Definition
Properties with a high proportion of heifers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Over 30 year old animals and • heifers of dairy breeds and crossbreeds make up min. 60% of all annuals
Slaughter calf 1 - small	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slaughter of 20-100 bull calves per years, and • dairy breed and crossbreed make up min. 80% of all annuals
Slaughter calf 2 - large	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slaughter of over 100 bull calves per years, and • dairy breed and crossbreed make up min. 80% of all annuals
Beef cattle 1 - small	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10-50 yearlings, and • cows make up min. 20% of all annual animals, and • beef cattle breed and crossbreed breed make up min. 80% of all annuals
Beef cattle 2 - large	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Over 50 yearlings, and • cows make up min. 20% of all annual animals, and • beef cattle breed and crossbreed breed make up min. 80% of all annuals
Other, small	• number of annual animals <10
Other, large	• 10 or more annual animals

Group	Total number of properties	Properties that are not in level 1	
		Quantity	Percentage
Properties with a high proportion of heifers	579	87	15.0%
Slaughter calf 1, small	266	18	6.8%
Slaughter calf 2, large	243	25	10.3%
Beef cattle 1, small	3,175	10	0.3%
Beef cattle 2, large	822	2	0.2%
Other small (<10 year old animals)	6,436	112	1.7%
Other large (=> 10 year old animals)	960	28	2.9%
Total	12,481	282	2.3%

Procent ikke-mælkeleverende i Dublin niveau 2+3 inkl. ukendt niveau

Figure 7: Distribution of non-dairy cattle herd classification stratified by S. Dublin Level and region (state of: 05.01.2022) Note that individual properties may meet the definitions in more than one group. In such a case, however, only one of the groups is selected - the group at the top of the table above is selected, i.e. the groups with slaughter calves are chosen over beef cattle and the group with properties with a high proportion of heifers is chosen over slaughter calves. The starting point is (up to) the last 8 blood tests that have been performed on the property or more commonly at slaughter. If one or more of these samples has an analysis value > 50 ODC%, then the property is declared to be infected. Properties with a high proportion of heifers are tested 1-2 times annually, typically on farm, because they do not send many cattle to the abattoirs. The groups were defined as of April 27, 2009.

Source 7: <http://www.kvaegvet.dk/>

The number of human recorded cases infected with S. Dublin stratified by year, gender, sex and region are available in the SSI Laboratory Notifiable Diseases database (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Human cases of S. Dublin

Source:

<https://statistik.ssi.dk/sygdomsdata#!/?sygdomskode=SALM&stype=9&xaxis=Aar&show=Graph&datatyp=Laboratory>

1.5. Deliverable 2

A modelling framework for the usage of S. Dublin output-based surveillance data

Test-strategies are best when they are herd-specific and dynamic, but this is not always possible at national level. While inputs can vary between surveillance programmes, the outputs need to be comparable within and across programmes. The classification of herds regarding infection status can be based on a wide variety of testing strategies in terms of the nature of the tests used (e.g., type of

diagnostic test), the groups of animals tested (e.g., dairy herds, non-dairy herds, calves), number of animals tested, frequency of testing but also changes in the surveillance programme (e.g. implementation of different intervention measures during the period). Even within a single programme, surveillance modalities may evolve over time, sensitivity and specificity of diagnostic test to determine the true positive and negative herd status is not 100%, and herds are heterogenous which can influence the diagnostic test results itself. For instance, larger herd size can cause a delay in the detection of antibodies due to their high dilution in large milk tanks. Consequently, herds with low antibodies can still be infected and infectious. The STOCfree modelling approach (see Madouasse *et al.*, 2021) is considered as a useful modelling framework to analyse *S. Dublin* output-based surveillance laboratory test data in combination with risk factors assigned to each individual cattle herd simultaneously in one model in order to improve the prediction of herd level probabilities of *S. Dublin* infections (and future test-positivity). The model outcome (Figure 9a) can be used to analyze the force of infection (i.e. transmission rates of different pathways) via different pathways. For instance, whether cattle movements, despite existing trade restrictions between cattle herds assigned into different *S. Dublin* levels, can explain the occurrence of new infections in the Danish cattle population (Figure 9b) (for instance through spread of infection from false-negative cattle herds in Level 1).

The average ODC% of four consecutive BTM samples and the ODC% in the most recent sample compared to the average of the previous three will be used to predict changes in the probabilities of *S. Dublin* infection for each cattle herd per months (results of the output-based surveillance programme). The quantities of interest are the herd level probabilities of being latent status positive (i.e. infected with *S. Dublin*. N.B. latent status means unknown cattle herd health status because e.g. not tested yet) on the last test month in the output-based surveillance dataset by considering test sensitivity, test specificity, and the risk factors of herds to become infected.

Between test events, uninfected herds can become infected and infected herds can clear the infection. The model represents the probability of being infected at each time step as a function of the status at the previous time step. For the first time step when herd status is assigned, there is no previous status against which to evaluate change. From the second time step when herd status is assigned, and onwards, herds that were status negative (i.e. non-infected based on negative test results) on the previous time step have a certain probability of becoming status positive (i.e. infected) and herds that were status positive (i.e. infected based on positive test results) have a certain probability of remaining status positive. The model represents infection as a herd latent status with a month dynamic based on four bulk tank milk test results. This latent status determines test results of the output-based surveillance programmes and associated test sensitivity and test specificity. The probability of becoming status positive between consecutive months is modelled as a function of risk factors. Modelling is performed in a Bayesian framework. Prior distributions need to be provided for the sensitivities and specificities of the different tests used (and used in combination; see for example prior distributions regarding *S. Dublin* in the study by Warnick *et al.*, 2006), for the probability of remaining status positive between months as well as for the probability of becoming infected between months. When risk factors are available, prior distributions need to be provided for the coefficients for the model, replacing the prior for the probability of becoming positive. From these prior distributions and from the longitudinal data, the model returns posterior probability distributions for being status positive for all herds on the current month (further information to the model provided in the study by Madouasse *et al.*, 2021 and Mercat *et al.*, 2022). Data from the previous months (e.g., every month or in another time interval) are used in the modelling framework for parameter estimation.

The main advantage of this model is its ability to predict a probability of being status positive in a month for each cattle herd from BTM, blood test, bacteriological inputs that can vary in terms of nature of test, frequency of testing and risk factor availability/presence. The Hidden Markov Model takes into account the time dynamics in the latent status (e.g. unknown herd status because laboratory test was not

performed). The probability of new infection between consecutive time steps is modelled as a function of risk factors (see Figure 9a). Each herd level status is re-evaluated when new data (most commonly test results but may also be data related to risk factors) are available. The estimation and prediction are performed within a Bayesian framework using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC).

The model encodes the relationships between all the variables of interest in a single model. Each variable is modelled as drawn from a statistical distribution. The estimation requires prior distributions for all the parameters in the model (output-based surveillance datasets). From the model specification, the prior distributions and the observed data, the MCMC algorithm draws samples from the posterior distributions of all the variables in the model. These posterior distributions are the probability distributions for the model parameters given the data and the prior distributions. At each iteration of the MCMC algorithm, given the data and priors, a herd status (0 or 1) and the coefficients for the associations between risk factors, latent status and test results are drawn from their posterior distribution (see more detail description: Madouasse *et al.*, 2021).

Prediction of herd-level probabilities of S. Dublin infection and spread of S. Dublin via Movements

Figure 9: **a)** Conceptual representation of the implementation of a surveillance programme within a herd. The focus of the model is the latent status regarding infection, which is modelled at the herd-month level. This status partly depends on risk factors and determines test results. In this diagram, risk factors are represented as green dots when present and available test results as blue shaded squares. The model predicts a probability of infection for the most recent month in the surveillance programme using all the data collected for the estimation of model parameters. Modelling of infection dynamics. The diagram (right) shows hypothetical latent statuses (0 for negative; 1 for positive) as a function of time in month, with examples of all possible transitions. $\pi_1 = p(S_1 = 1)$ is the probability of being status positive at the first point in time, $\tau_1 = p(S_t = 1 | S_{t-1} = 0)$ is the probability of becoming status positive and $\tau_2 = p(S_t = 1 | S_{t-1} = 1)$ is the probability of remaining status positive (Source: Madouasse *et al.*, 2021). **b)** Cattle herds with different probability of infections per time step can be assigned into different health compartments S (Susceptible; free of S. Dublin; level 1), I_d (Infected and detected), I_{nd_ni} (Infected but not detected due to low antibody level and not infectious) and I_{nd_i} (Infected and not detected but infectious due to increased antibodies over the testing results) and R compartment (Recovered), whereby recovered herds can move back to S after eradication of S. Dublin. The transmission probability of each farm can be further weights according to the type of consignments i.e. weather calves, young or adults animals are traded between farms which will influence the force of infections.

Cattle herds with different probabilities of infection per time step can be assigned to different health compartments S (Susceptible; free of *S. Dublin*), Id (Infected and detected), Ind_{ni} (Infected but not detected due to low antibody level and not infectious), Ind_i (Infected and not detected but infectious due to increased antibodies over the testing results) and R compartment (Recovered), whereby R herds can move back to S after eradication of *S. Dublin*. The compartments can be extended further with the fact that some herds can be infectious despite low antibodies or without having an increase in antibodies for a period (referred to as a delay period before an increase in antibodies is observed). The assignment of the herd health compartments can be based on thresholds of the probabilities of infection (ranged between 1 maximum risk (Ind_I) and 0 minimum risk (S)).

The herd health compartments in a specific time step t can be compared with the real cattle movements, including the trade bans between the herds of different *S. Dublin* levels 1 and 2. The comparison will provide information on how many of the new infections are related to animal movements (the force of infection via cattle movements) despite existing trade restrictions by considering not only test results but also delay in assignment of herds in the correct *S. Dublin* levels due to antibody lag periods, accuracy of the laboratory tests in combination with associated risk factors for each herd.

The assigned health compartments for each cattle herd to a specific time step t can be compared with the associated real cattle movements including the trade bans between herds with different *S. Dublin* levels. The comparison will provide information how many of the new infections are related to animal movements (the force of infection (i.e. transmission rate via cattle movements)) despite existing trade restrictions considering in addition to test results also that a herd can become infected between testing results, the accuracy of the laboratory tests in combination with associated heterogeneous cattle herd risk factors.

The following risk factors should be included in the calculation of the probability of *S. Dublin* infection, adjusted for each cattle herd:

1. **Herd size:** On the one hand, larger herd size can cause a delay in the detection of antibodies due to their high dilution in large milk tanks. On the other hand, a larger herd size will increase the probability of infection compared to cattle herds with a low herd size because the number of transmission pathways within the herd via contacts is higher. This might influence the movement of cattle herds between level 1 and level 2. Additionally, the herd size might be correlated with the manure production i.e. with the growth of *S. Dublin* pathogen in the environment.
2. **History of infections:** The probability of *S. Dublin* infection is higher if a farm has *S. Dublin* infection in the past. The probability is adjusted in relation to "how long the infection goes back". For instance, if a farm has been recently assigned to level 1 the probability of returning back to level 2 is higher compared to farms that stay for a very long period in the same *S. Dublin* level.
3. **Neighbouring infection:** The closer a farm is to another infected farm, the higher the probability of infection (geographic location).
4. **Herd composition:** Calves may increase the probability of infections of a herd.
5. **Season:** Seasons with high temperature and humidity are associated with a higher growth of *S. Dublin* pathogen in the environment.
6. **Biosecurity measures:** A high biosecurity level would decrease the probability of infections, but biosecurity status is not available for each cattle farm (in contrast to many Danish pig herds). A field study covers 120 Danish cattle farms, thereof 40 newly infected with *S. Dublin* in 2021-2022. Therefore, it is necessary to make assumptions or extrapolate from the farm level to the national level.
7. **Production type:** Organic vs. conventional.
8. **Business farms:** It is not mandatory to report animal movements of a farm which cover several farms within 4 km radius.

Further, it is recommended i) to calculate the probability of infection for all risk factors together; ii) each risk factor separately and iii) to choose different length of periods to predict the probability of herd infections (test datasets) and iv) to choose different length of periods of trade movement snapshots for comparison. This will allow analysis of the impact of the risk factors on the probability of infections and provide recommendation about the robustness of the method.

The suggested modelling framework can i) improve the application and comparison of output-based surveillance data by combination of heterogenous laboratory test data with individual herd risk factors and ii) quantify whether new *S. Dublin* infections are related to cattle movements despite existing trade bans between *S. Dublin* infected and non-infected cattle farms (Figure 9). The advantage of this approach is that the heterogeneity of herds regarding test results and risk factors is simultaneously considered in one model. This can influence the probability of infections compared to output-based-surveillance programme taken. In the official *S. Dublin* control programme, the laboratory test results are the main factor for the assignment of the herds into free or non-free of *S. Dublin* (level 1 and 2) including violations of trading restrictions (see 1.3 background information).

The disadvantage is that the public domain datasets (Deliverable 1) are less appropriate for the suggested modelling approach, since time-resolved laboratory results of output-based surveillance programmes with associated time-resolved risk factors are needed for each cattle herd in order to predict the probability of infections. Furthermore, the method is very sensitive to the choice of the length of historical datasets used as test data for prediction of the herd status of infections in different periods and associated number of infected cases. Further, the model can be used to simulate the effect of different control measures related to animal movements, such as to reduce the spread of *S. Dublin*, or related to testing strategies such as changing cut-offs in BTM or blood samples in order to detect potential undetected but infected cattle farms.

2. Case study 2 – *Salmonella* in layer flocks

2.1. Output based modelling for endemic disease: European Union (EU) National Control Programme in commercial laying flocks

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(*Table and figure numbers are consecutive for this case study only)

2.2. Introduction

The EU has an active animal health policy and supports Member States (MS) to eradicate, control and monitor notifiable diseases. EU wide control programmes are typically associated with input-based surveillance. That is, they tend to specify the level of testing that needs to be done in terms of the level of sampling and number of herds that require sampling. The disadvantage of this approach is that it does not take into account the specific context of that country in terms of factors such as population density, contact structure and disease prevalence. An alternative approach is the use of OBS to determine the surveillance scheme. These prescribe what the surveillance must achieve rather than what surveillance activities should be performed. By focusing on what needs to be achieved, output-based surveillance can result in optimally designed, cost-effective and socially accepted control programmes (Cameron 2012; WOA 2019). The aim of this study was to apply an OBS approach to an EU-wide control programme for an endemic pathogen, specifically the National Control Programme (NCP) for *Salmonella* in commercial laying flocks, to illustrate the potential for use of an OBS for the design of a surveillance programme.

The NCP for *Salmonella* in commercial laying flocks consists of a combination of two types of sampling, samples taken by the operator of the flock (Operator sampling) and those taken by the competent authority (CA Official sampling). Controls are implemented on farms that test positive for the 2 regulated serovars *Salmonella* Enteritidis (SE) and *Salmonella* Typhimurium (ST), and there is a currently a target of a 2% flock prevalence for these serovars for the United Kingdom (UK) based on overall annual testing results. Operator sampling is required on all holdings with 350 birds or more. The first Operator sample during the laying period is taken between 22-26 weeks flock age and one sample is taken either every 13 weeks thereafter for flocks registered with the Lion Code assurance scheme or every 15 weeks thereafter for other flocks. CA Official samples are collected at a random age from 1 flock per annum on each holding with over 1,000 birds. The sampling methods used in the NCP are much less sensitive at farm level than an alternative approach, Veterinary Laboratory Agency (VLA), UK, (now Animal and Plant health Agency (APHA)) sampling (Arnold *et al.*, 2010; Arnold *et al.*, 2011), which consists of 10-20 large faecal swabs and 10-20 large dust swabs from around the house. In particular, there have been issues identified with the performance of Operator sampling across the EU (EFSA 2019), suggesting that the use of an alternative approach with greater farm sensitivity might be more effective. Therefore, the aim of this study was to explore the use of an output-based surveillance scheme for *Salmonella* in egg-laying flocks using VLA sampling on farms. Specifically, the number of farms required to sample using VLA samples in order to match the precision of the prevalence estimate that arises from the NCP was calculated i.e. the aim of the output based surveillance to match sensitivity of the current NCP.

2.3. Methods

2.3.1.1. Modelling Overview

A statistical modelling framework was built to evaluate the precision of the estimation of *Salmonella* prevalence of (i) the NCP for *Salmonella* in commercial egg-laying flocks (input-based surveillance) and (ii) sampling a number of flocks using VLA sampling. Two steps were involved in estimating the precision of the prevalence estimation (Figure 1). Firstly, surveillance data was simulated using an assumed

proportion of holdings infected and assumed test sensitivities for the NCP and VLA sampling. Secondly, the simulated data was used as an input to Bayesian models that estimated the proportion of infected holdings and the associated 95% Bayesian credible interval.

It was assumed that 5% of layer holdings were infected. In reality, this level of prevalence would be more representative of all *Salmonella* serovars rather than the 2 target serovars of SE/ST, but the level of prevalence had no influence on the relative performance of NCP vs VLA surveillance, and the 5% level was chosen merely to be illustrative. The sensitivity of NCP and VLA sampling was taken from a previous research study (Arnold *et al.*, 2010); the published values were used as actual for the simulation of surveillance data and as priors for the Bayesian estimation.

Figure 1. Outline of the modelling process used to evaluate the precision of the prevalence estimation for the National Control Programme (NCP) for *Salmonella* in commercial egg-laying flocks and for sampling a proportion of farms with VLA sampling.

2.3.1.2. NCP sampling method

The methods of collection, processing and culture of NCP samples were laid out in Commission Regulation (EC) No 1168/2006. Sampling consists of two faeces samples, each representing half of the house which are then pooled. These samples may come from manure belts, or two 150g samples of naturally pooled faeces from the floor of the house (caged flocks), or from two pairs of boot swabs (non-cage flocks). For a CA Official sample, an additional sample of 150 grams naturally pooled faeces or an additional pair of boot swabs was taken.

2.3.1.3. VLA sampling method

The VLA sampling method is a highly sensitive method for *Salmonella* detection in a flock (Arnold *et al.*, 2010). It usually consists of taking 10-20 litter swabs and an equal number of dust swabs, depending on the size of the poultry house. As dust is not always available, and also appeared to have lower sensitivity post introduction of the NCP (Arnold *et al.*, 2014), we assumed a uniform approach of taking 20 litter swabs per flock, collected from representative locations in each house. Swab samples consisted of approximately 25g of naturally mixed faeces from droppings belts, scrapers or deep pits (step cage systems). More detail on the sampling methods and the method of culture can be found in (Carrique-Mas *et al.*, 2008a).

2.3.1.4. Bayesian model to estimate prevalence of infected holdings

A previously developed statistical model of NCP surveillance in commercial laying flocks (unpublished) was used to infer holding prevalence from the simulated NCP data. In short, this model took into account the number of Operator and CA Official samples, the sensitivity of the Operator and CA Official sampling, and the number of samples positive by age-group to estimate the sensitivity of Operator and CA Official sampling, the holding prevalence and the within-flock prevalence by age-group.

It was assumed that the sensitivity of NCP and VLA samples to detect *Salmonella* varies according to the proportion of birds in the flock that are infected and was described by a logistic regression relationship as found in previous studies (Arnold *et al.*, 2010; Arnold *et al.*, 2011). As positive samples were confirmed via bacterial typing, specificity was assumed to be 100%. Two different assumptions were made regarding the within-flock prevalence to see what impact this had on the relative performance of each of the different surveillance scenarios: (i) mean of 10.7%, in line with that estimated from 20 farms sampled post introduction of the NCP in an APHA research study (Arnold *et al.*, 2014) and (ii) mean of 1.0%, taken from the 10 farms with the lowest infection prevalence from the research study (Arnold *et al.*, 2014), to represent the possible reduction in within-farm prevalence on layer farms due to control measures introduced in response to the NCP. Holdings could consist of more than 1 flock, with the distribution of the number of flocks per holding taken from APHA data, and the mean number of infected flocks on infected holdings assumed to be on average 74%, in line with a previous study in Great Britain (GB) (Carrique-Mas *et al.*, 2008b). The number of positive holdings per annum from the NCP then follows a binomial distribution depending on the holding level sensitivity, the number of holdings sampled and the prevalence of infected holdings.

A key feature of Bayesian modelling is that results from previous studies can be incorporated into the parameter estimates via the use of priors, which represent what is known about them before the analysis of the study data. Prior distributions were largely taken from previous studies looking at sensitivity of NCP faecal sampling and how it depends upon the within-flock prevalence and an analysis of EU survey data (Table 1). The true prevalence of *Salmonella* was assumed uncertain (a value of 0.05 was used for the simulations) and a vague prior representing a uniform distribution between 0 and 1 was used (by employing a beta prior with both parameters equal to 1).

The prior for within-flock prevalence, an important parameter since it influences the sensitivity of NCP sampling, was derived from a study of 15 flocks post introduction of the NCP (Arnold *et al.*, 2014). A beta distribution, which is a flexible statistical distribution with values between 0 and 1 (so, useful at representing infection prevalence), was fitted to the set of 15 infection prevalence estimates, which had a mean of 9.5%, resulting in a beta distribution with parameters given by 0.71 and 6.76 (Table 1). The posterior distributions were taken from 10,000 iterations of WinBUGS 3.1, using a burn-in of 5,000 iterations.

Table 1 The prior assumptions for each of the model parameters of a Bayesian model to estimate the prevalence of *Salmonella* infection in flocks of laying hens in GB.

Parameter	Description	Value	Source
$\alpha_{NCP}, \beta_{NCP}$	Priors for the sensitivity of NCP faecal samples	$\alpha_f \sim N(-0.95, 1.22)$ $\beta_f \sim N(11.61, 5.77)$	[4, 7]
$\alpha_{VLA}, \beta_{VLA}$	Priors for the sensitivity of VLA faecal samples	$\alpha_f \sim N(-1.93, 0.1)$ $\beta_f \sim N(5.25, 0.33)$	[5]

Parameter	Description	Value	Source
λ_i	Within-flock prevalence	$\lambda_i \sim \text{beta}(0.71, 6.76)$	Beta distribution fitted to results from [7]
a	Holding level <i>Salmonella</i> prevalence (non-SE/ST) in 2009	$a \sim \text{beta}(1,1)$	Uninformative.

Results of operator vs CA Official sampling from EU member states have shown that CA Official samples have an approximately 10-fold greater rate of being positive than operator samples in the case of broiler and carcass samples (EFSA 2019). If the same low relative sensitivity of operator sampling also applies in the case of laying flocks, this could impact the performance of the NCP and consequently the performance of VLA sampling relative to that of the NCP. Therefore, the impact of this lower sensitivity of Operator sampling on the width of the credible interval for holding prevalence was explored. It is also possible that the sensitivity of Operator sampling may differ from the published studies, owing to country-level effects and other factors may have influenced the performance of environmental sampling over time. Therefore, the models for VLA and NCP sampling were fitted using vague priors for the sensitivity, to see how high levels of uncertainty in the prior influenced the prevalence estimation and its uncertainty.

The target reduction in holding prevalence for the UK, based on the prevalence found in the baseline survey (EFSA 2007), was 10% per annum for SE/ST. Therefore, the power of the NCP to determine the reduction based on data from consecutive years was estimated, and the number of farms needing to be sampled to match this using VLA sampling was calculated. The precision of the annual reduction in holding infection prevalence was estimated for 200, 400, 600, 800 and 1,000 farms sampled each with 20 VLA faeces samples, and the dependence of the width of the credible interval on the number of farms sampled estimated using linear regression.

2.4. Results

While there were only minimal differences in the estimate of the proportion of holdings infected with *Salmonella* VLA sampling (regardless of the number of farms sampled) and the *Salmonella* NCP (Fig.2), there were big differences in the width of the credible intervals. Where it was assumed that both VLA and NCP sampling had sensitivities equal to those found in research studies (Arnold *et al.*, 2010; Arnold *et al.*, 2014), the VLA sampling of a subset of the layer holdings resulted in much wider credible intervals than the NCP sampling, of all the holdings for both the scenario where within flock prevalence had a mean of 10.6% (Fig.2, left hand (LH) plot) and where within flock prevalence had a mean of 1.0% (Fig.2, right hand (RH) plot).

Figure 2. How the width of the credible interval for the prevalence of farms infected with *Salmonella* varied for different numbers of farms sampled with VLA sampling, compared with NCP sampling for (i) assuming a within-flock prevalence of 10% (LH plot) and (ii) assuming a within flock prevalence of 1% (RH plot).

Where the Operator sampling was assumed to have a much lower sensitivity than CA Official sampling, in line with findings from the apparent rate of positivity of Operator samples across the EU, then the NCP surveillance was equivalent to sampling around 600 holdings using VLA sampling, in terms of each having a similar precision for the estimation of holding prevalence (Fig.3a). The inclusion of vague priors for the sensitivity of VLA and NCP sampling had a large impact on the upper credible interval of the holding prevalence (Fig.3b), with some model iterations having a very wide credible interval. In this case VLA sampling of a sample of flocks would result in higher precision of the holding level prevalence.

Figure 3. How the width of the credible interval for the prevalence of commercial layer holdings infected with *Salmonella* varied for different numbers of farms sampled with VLA sampling, compared with NCP sampling assuming a) Operator sampling is as 1/10th as sensitive as CA Official sampling and b) as a) but assuming vague priors for sample sensitivity.

In terms of using the NCP to estimate the annual proportionate reduction in *Salmonella* holding prevalence, the resulting estimate of the rate of decline of infection prevalence between two successive years was given by 0.91 (95% CrI: 0.56-1.45). For VLA sampling of a number of farms, the width of the credible interval of the annual reduction was given by $1.88 - 0.0014n$, where n is the number of farms sampled using 20 VLA faeces samples (Fig.4). To match the precision of the annual proportionate reduction provided by NCP sampling, 687 farms would need to be sampled using VLA sampling.

Figure 4. Width of the credible interval of the estimate of the reduction in holding prevalence for different numbers of holdings sampled with VLA samples.

2.5. Discussion

The study shows that, where assumed test sensitivities are based on studies carried out prior to the introduction of the NCP, the design of the NCP leads to a highly effective surveillance programme, identifying the vast majority of flocks. In fact, even with the much lower apparent sensitivity of Operator sampling that is found across the EU, the model still estimates that a large proportion of infected flocks are detected. This is partly due to the fact that Operator sampling, although having a relatively low sensitivity compared to CA Official sampling, is carried out on each flock and will be done 4 times per annum per flock. However, the estimated precision of the *Salmonella* NCP and proportion of infected holdings detected is dependent on CA Official sampling having a sensitivity comparable to that found in previous research studies (Arnold *et al.*, 2010; Arnold *et al.*, 2014), where it would be expected to have a sensitivity of around 80%. If this sensitivity were to be significantly lower than this, combined with the apparent sensitivity of Operator sample sensitivity being around 1/10th of that of CA Official sampling, this would have a large impact on the estimated power of the surveillance.

VLA sampling is a more time-efficient sampling method on farm than Operator sampling, with each sample being quicker to take and no pooling of samples required. However, VLA sampling would be more costly to implement than Operator sampling as would require 20-40 cultures instead of the 1 culture required for Operator sampling. Its large advantage over the NCP sampling is that it has higher

sensitivity per flock than the NCP sample types, and as there are multiple samples taken it is less affected by a reduction in within-flock prevalence than the NCP samples. Assuming that it is cultured within a government laboratory, there is also greater certainty over its overall sensitivity than the NCP sample types. However, given the greater costs involved it is unlikely to be adopted as a replacement for Operator sampling. However, it could be considered as a sampling method to be adopted for unannounced CA Official sampling.

In the present study we assumed 20 faeces per flock for the VLA sampling method. In practice, where dust is available to collect within a flock, then half the samples collected would be dust samples. Prior to the introduction of the NCP dust had been found to be a more sensitive method than faeces (Arnold *et al.*, 2010), but a study carried out post-introduction of the NCP found that dust in non-cage flocks had low sensitivity (Arnold *et al.*, 2014) and so it is unclear whether the use of dust would increase or reduce the sensitivity of VLA sampling, and it might depend upon the flock type.

One advantage of output-based surveillance is that one can tailor the surveillance scheme to meet a specific objective. In the case of this study this means for example, one can specify the power with which one estimates the likelihood of a specific reduction in *Salmonella* prevalence or the width of the credible interval of the true infection prevalence. For the NCP, the power of the surveillance is limited by the sensitivity of the test and its associated uncertainty. This is particularly an issue where the Operator sampling has performed less well in practice than in research studies carried out prior to the NCP.

3. Case study 3 – *Salmonella* in pigs

3.1. Evaluation of the case finding capacity of the *Salmonella* surveillance programme for Swedish pigs

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(*Table and figure numbers are consecutive for this case study only)

3.2. Introduction

A salmonella control programme for food-producing animals has been in place for over 60 years in Sweden. The overall goal of the programme is to protect human health by ensuring that food products of animal origin are free from *Salmonella*. The programme covers the entire chain from feed to food, with sampling occurring at all levels. The control programme has been very successful and official statistics on the number of human cases show that the number of people domestically infected by *Salmonella* each year is low in comparison to other countries (EFSA and ECDC, 2021).

The Swedish *Salmonella* control programme has resulted in a low prevalence of *Salmonella* in animal production herds, including pig herds. This has been confirmed in baseline prevalence studies performed on behalf of the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) (EFSA, 2008; EFSA, 2009). However, pig production in Sweden has changed over time, including a trend toward there being fewer but larger herds. The *Salmonella* situation in Swedish pig herds has also seen recent changes. For example, in 2020-2021, *Salmonella* was detected in several very large herds and the resulting investigations and elimination efforts in these herds became extremely costly for both the Swedish state and the pig industry. Also in 2020, the pig-adapted serotype *Salmonella choleraesuis* was identified in domestic pigs for the first time in over 40 years (National Veterinary Institute, 2021). These events have led to a need to review the current *Salmonella* control programme in pigs, including the existing *Salmonella* surveillance system. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of the different components of the *Salmonella* surveillance system that are used to identify pig herds infected with *Salmonella*.

3.3. Materials and methods

3.3.1.1. Description of the current *Salmonella* surveillance programme components for Swedish pigs

The current *Salmonella* surveillance programme to identify Swedish pigs for control measures consists of several components that can be divided into either passive or active monitoring. The passive components include the clinical surveillance of sick and dead animals that are sampled for *Salmonella* testing. According to Swedish legislation, when *Salmonella* is suspected in pigs on the basis of clinical signs, the suspicion must be reported, and samples taken by a veterinarian for *Salmonella* testing. The passive component also includes sampling at post-mortem facilities where samples must be submitted for *Salmonella* analysis if *Salmonella* is suspected due to post-mortem findings. Infection with *Salmonella choleraesuis* can result in severe clinical signs and high mortality in pigs. However, this serotype is rarely found in Swedish pigs. In 2020, *S. choleraesuis* was detected in a sow herd but, prior to this, the serotype had not been identified in Swedish pigs since the end of the 1970's (National Veterinary Institute, 2021). Other *Salmonella* serotypes only rarely cause clinical disease in pigs, and they seldom produce pathological changes that can be seen during post-mortem examination. For these reasons, the utility of the clinical disease and post-mortem components of the *Salmonella* surveillance programme are considered to be limited in Swedish pigs (Jordbruksverket, 2007).

Therefore, it was decided that the passive components of the surveillance program would not be included in this evaluation.

The active components of the salmonella surveillance program in pigs include a) sampling in nucleus and gilt multiplying herds, b) sampling in sow pools, c) testing of lymph nodes sampled at abattoirs, and d) contact tracing from infected herds and humans or contaminated food and feed. Within all active components, the surveillance is based on culturing for the presence of salmonella bacteria. This evaluation includes only those surveillance components that are designed to detect index or primary cases of salmonella in pig herds and not those designed to detect secondary cases (i.e. contact tracing). Therefore, only the first three active surveillance components named above (a, b, and c) are included in this evaluation.

3.3.1.2. Method for evaluation of the case-finding capacity (CFC) of current surveillance programme components

For this evaluation, the number of *Salmonella*-infected pig herds that can be expected to be identified within the various surveillance components were calculated. The calculations were based on expected prevalence (see below), probability that an infected herd is detected by the current surveillance component (sensitivity at the herd level) and the number of herds examined within each surveillance component.

We used a method developed by Cameron and co-workers and used by EFSA to assess the contribution of meat inspection to animal disease surveillance (Dupuy *et al.*, 2012). It is similar to scenario-tree modelling for demonstrating disease freedom (Martin *et al.*, 2007), but with CFC as the main outcome instead of system sensitivity. It is based on proportions of different strata of the population, differences in risk of infection between different strata of the population, and probabilities of events throughout the chain of events within each surveillance component. The detection fraction (DF) was the fraction of cases expected to be detected out of the total number of expected cases within each surveillance component. The incremental benefit of each component took population coverage and overlap of surveillance components into account.

3.3.1.3. Input values

The input values used to calculate the number of cases that can be expected to be identified within the existing surveillance components are shown in Table 1. In addition, background information and explanations for each input value are found below for each of the surveillance components.

Table 1: Input values used to calculate the number of infected herds that each surveillance component of the *Salmonella* control programme in Swedish pigs is expected to detect

Surveillance component	Description	Value
Sampling of nucleus and gilt multiplying herds; sampling of sow pools	Herd-level expected prevalence	0.05
	Within-herd expected prevalence	0.15
	Diagnostic sensitivity of <i>Salmonella</i> culture at the individual level	0.3
	Reduction factor for sensitivity with pooling of samples	0.85
	Pool sensitivity	0.26
	Pool specificity	1
Sampling of lymph nodes at slaughter	Herd-level expected prevalence	0.05
	Probability that a herd is sampled (at least one pig)	1

Surveillance component	Description	Value
	Probability that a pig sent to slaughter from an infected herd tests positive on lymph node sampling (ie pos pool)	0.12
	Probability that <i>Salmonella</i> is reisolated from a positive lymph node pool	0.76
	Probability that an infected herd tests positive on a follow-up herd sampling	0.885

3.3.1.4. Design prevalence

The calculations in this evaluation are based on, among other parameters, the expected prevalence in the population, which is the performance measure against which the sensitivity of the surveillance is evaluated. It can be specified both at the within- and between-herd level.

There have been no recent evaluations of the *Salmonella* prevalence in Swedish pig herds. A baseline study that produced estimates of *Salmonella* prevalence in pig herds that allowed for comparisons between EU MSs was conducted in 2008. In that study, *Salmonella* was detected in faecal samples from 1/57 (1.8%) Swedish herds with sows (EFSA, 2009). For other forms of pig production, prevalence studies in Sweden are completely lacking. Since the time that the baseline study was completed, there have been many changes to the Swedish pig industry which may have affected *Salmonella* prevalence. Thus, the between-herd prevalence was estimated through expert opinion to be 5%. According to the Swedish Board of Agriculture's statistics database, there were 1187 pig herds in Sweden in 2021. Therefore, a design prevalence of 5% would correspond to a total of 59 salmonella-infected pig herds.

The within-herd prevalence (used to calculate the herd sensitivity) was estimated at 15%. The estimation was based on the opinion of experts at the National Veterinary Institute and was based on the fact that approximately 5 percent of samples are positive when sampling is done in pig herds that have been placed under restrictions due to *Salmonella* in combination with an individual test sensitivity of 30 percent (Ågren *et al.*, 2018).

3.3.1.5. Relative risk

None of the *Salmonella* surveillance components for Swedish pigs are risk-based. Therefore, the risk of *Salmonella* infection was considered to be equal across all strata.

3.3.1.6. Description of input values for each salmonella surveillance component (SC) for Swedish pigs

1. Sampling in nucleus and gilt multiplier herds – SC1

This component of the *Salmonella* surveillance programme is aimed at herds in which the presence of *Salmonella* could have major consequences. Herds at the top of the Swedish breeding pyramid undergo mandatory annual *Salmonella* testing. Within this annual testing, faecal samples are collected from 50 adult animals in each herd, which are pooled by 5 into 10 pooled samples for analysis by culture. In 2021, there were 22 nucleus and multiplier herds in Sweden, all of which were included in this surveillance component (personal communication, G. Johansson, February 3, 2022).

Information on the diagnostic sensitivity of *Salmonella* culturing at the individual level is lacking for pigs. In cattle, diagnostic sensitivity for culturing *Salmonella Dublin* has been estimated at 10-50% with a most likely value of 30% (Ågren *et al.*, 2018). These figures have been used in this evaluation. The faecal samples taken in this surveillance component are pooled and pooling may have an effect on the sensitivity of the analysis. A reduction factor of 85% for the sensitivity of pooled samples has been used in the calculations (Lombard *et al.*, 2012). Pool sensitivity is therefore calculated at 26% (sensitivity of

individual culture * reduction factor = $30\% * 85\% = 26\%$). Specificity for culturing pooled samples was assumed to be 100%.

2. Sampling in sow pools – SC2

This surveillance component, like the above, is aimed at herds in which *Salmonella* infection could have major consequences. In the Swedish sow pool system of production, breeding and gestation occurs in a centralized “hub” which owns the sows, while farrowing and growing pig production occurs in a number of decentralized “satellite” herds that rent pregnant sows from the hub. There is therefore a continuous flow of sows between each hub and its satellite herds.

Testing in sow pools is similar to that for nucleus and multiplier herds, with the only difference being that sow pools are sampled twice per year instead of once. The input values used in the calculations for sow pool surveillance were therefore the same as those used in the nucleus and multiplier herd surveillance. All sampling occurs in the sow pool hubs. There are currently 14 sow pools in Sweden (personal communication, G. Johansson, February 3, 2022) with approximately 60 satellite herds (personal communication, J. Fjelkner, February 14, 2022) so, in total, 74 herds are covered by this surveillance component.

3. Sampling at abattoirs – SC3

There is also an active *Salmonella* surveillance component that occurs at abattoirs through sampling of lymph nodes collected from carcasses. This component covers animals from all herds that send pigs to slaughter, including finisher pigs and adult cull animals. All 1187 pig herds in Sweden are considered to be covered by this surveillance component, including those that are covered by the surveillance in nucleus and multiplier herds and sow pools.

Mesenteric lymph nodes from at least 3000 adult pigs and 3000 finisher pigs are tested for *Salmonella* annually. These samples are part of the approximate 21 000 samples that are taken each year at abattoirs from pigs, cattle and poultry. This surveillance is designed to detect *Salmonella* at a national prevalence of 0.1% with 95% certainty. Sampling at each abattoir is proportional to its annual slaughter volume. Five mesenteric lymph nodes (5 lymph nodes = 1 sample) are collected from each pig that is selected for testing. Samples from a maximum of 10 animals may be pooled into one pooled sample for analysis by culture.

This surveillance component, which is primarily designed to provide evidence of a low *Salmonella* prevalence in carcasses at slaughter, is also used to identify herds suspected to be infected with *Salmonella*. If *Salmonella* is detected in a pool of lymph node samples, stored samples from the lymph nodes that were included in the positive pool are cultured again individually. If *Salmonella* is subsequently detected in an individual lymph node, then faecal sampling and culture are performed in the positive animals' herd of origin to confirm or rule-out *Salmonella* infection in the herd.

The probability that a herd is tested for *Salmonella* by sampling lymph nodes from at least one animal sent for slaughter from the herd was estimated at 100%. This was estimated by dividing the total number of pigs sampled by the total number of pig herds. In 2021, 3417 adult pigs and 3146 finisher pigs were tested through lymph node sampling (National Veterinary Institute, 2021). According to the Swedish Board of Agriculture statistics database, there were 1187 pig herds in Sweden in 2021 ($6563/1187 = 5.5$). As this result is >1 the probability of a herd being tested via the abattoir surveillance component was estimated to be 100% i.e. 5.5 pigs per herd would be tested per year. It was assumed that all herds have an equal probability of being sampled, but this may not actually be the case. There is no information on how the selection of animals for lymph node testing is carried out and whether the abattoirs take into account such factors as herd identity or herd size when animals are selected for testing. It can therefore

not be ruled out that sampling is carried out on more animals from certain herds, especially large herds that routinely send more animals to slaughter.

There is a lack of information that can be used to estimate the probability that a pig sent for slaughter from a *Salmonella*-infected herd is infected and tests positive on lymph node culture. For this reason, corresponding numbers from a previous report on the *Salmonella* surveillance system for Swedish cattle have been used (Zoonossynk, 2014). That report used results from studies on sensitivity of culturing lymph node samples from cattle, as well as studies that estimated within-herd prevalence among cattle, to estimate the probability that an animal sent for slaughter from a *Salmonella*-infected cattle herd tests positive on lymph node culture to be 4-20%.

When testing lymph nodes taken within the abattoir surveillance, samples are pooled for culture, with lymph nodes from up to 10 animals included in one pool. When a lymph node pool is positive, samples from all the lymph nodes included in the positive pool are cultured individually in order to identify which animal is positive so its herd of origin can be identified. In some cases, it is not possible to re-isolate *Salmonella* bacteria from the individual lymph nodes and therefore no individual herd can be identified for further sampling. The probability that *Salmonella* bacteria can be re-isolated in an individual lymph node from a positive lymph node pool was estimated to be 76%. This number was also taken from the Zoonossynk report (2014) which showed that between 1996-2013, the proportion of *Salmonella*-positive pools where *Salmonella* could be re-isolated from individual lymph nodes from cattle was 76%, with a range of 50-100%. This is in line with figures from 2020 which show that *Salmonella* was re-isolated in individual lymph node culture from 14/17 (82%) positive lymph node pools from pigs (personal communication, E. Lahti, February 28, 2022).

If *Salmonella* is re-isolated from an individual lymph node, the herd from which the animal was sent to slaughter is tested through a follow-up faecal sampling of the herd. Again, due to a lack of information about the probability of a *Salmonella*-infected pig herd testing positive during a follow-up sampling, this number was taken from the Zoonossynk report (2014). The report estimated the probability that a *Salmonella*-infected cattle herd tests positive for *Salmonella* during herd follow-up faecal testing to be 88.5%.

3.4. Results

The results of the case-finding capacity analysis indicates that each of the *Salmonella* surveillance components for pigs is expected to detect only a few *Salmonella* cases per year (Table 2). The calculations show that *Salmonella* is expected to be detected in approximately 9 herds each year. Sampling of lymph nodes at slaughter is expected to detect the most *Salmonella* cases, followed by sampling in sow pools and then sampling in nucleus and gilt multiplying herds.

Table 2: Results of the calculation of the number of *Salmonella*-infected pig herds that are expected to be detected by each surveillance component of the *Salmonella* control programme for pigs in Sweden

Surveillance Component	Detection fraction (proportion of positive herds expected to be detected by surveillance component)	Case finding capacity (number of truly positive herds expected to be detected by each surveillance component)
SC1 - Sampling in nucleus and gilt multiplying herds	1.48%	0.9
SC2 - Sampling in sow pools	5.94%	3.5
SC3 - Sampling of lymph nodes at slaughter	8.07%	4.8
Overall surveillance system	14.9%	8.8

3.5. Discussion

The Swedish *Salmonella* control program covers the entire food production chain. It includes sampling at different levels and requires follow-up measures if samples are found positive. The goal of the *Salmonella* control programme is the production of *Salmonella*-free food products of animal origin. In this study, we have focused on primary pig production and wanted to investigate the ability of the different components of the *Salmonella* surveillance program to identify *Salmonella*-infected pig herds. The surveillance of pig herds is primarily designed to identify herds where an infection could cause further spread in primary production. Therefore, sampling in herds takes place within the top of the breeding pyramid and in sow pools.

With a herd-level *Salmonella* prevalence of 5% and a total of 1187 pig herds, it is expected that 59 Swedish herds are infected with *Salmonella*. The results of the calculations show that the surveillance components examined detect only a low proportion (~15%) of the herds that are expected to be infected. There are, however, uncertainties about the chosen herd-level prevalence, and it may be that it was set too high. An on-going baseline study with serological sampling in a large number of pig herds is expected to provide a basis for a better estimate of the herd prevalence of *Salmonella* in Swedish pig herds. It should also be noted that this study did not examine all components of the *Salmonella* surveillance program for primary pig production. Neither the passive components of the program nor the contact tracing components were considered in this study, and these components also contribute to the detection of *Salmonella*-infected pig herds each year. Additionally, *Salmonella* surveillance occurs in other segments of the pork production chain, including feed production and at abattoirs and meat cutting facilities. The results of sampling done at abattoirs show that overall, the Swedish *Salmonella* control programme meets its goal of producing safe pork products that are free from *Salmonella*.

Between the years 2017-2021, *Salmonella* was detected in a total of 14 pig herds (2.8 herds per year) in Sweden through the surveillance components evaluated in this study, which indicates that the calculations may have overestimated the ability of the surveillance components to detect *Salmonella* cases. There are large uncertainties in the calculations of sensitivity of the various surveillance components. This is because each surveillance component consists of several steps and, for many of these steps, there is only limited information or a complete lack of information necessary to assess the probability. This necessitated the use of data extrapolated from cattle. In addition, there are uncertainties in the true prevalence of *Salmonella* in pigs.

Although the actual values for each surveillance component contain large uncertainties, the analysis makes it possible to compare the different surveillance components with each other. The results show that the surveillance component where the most *Salmonella*-positive herds are expected to be detected is through follow-up of positive findings in the abattoir monitoring component. This is also the surveillance component that includes the most herds (all herds in Sweden) and where the most samples are taken. This is in line with how *Salmonella* has actually been detected in pig herds over the past five years in Sweden. Between 2017-2021, *Salmonella* was detected in 12 herds as a result of positive findings in lymph node sampling at abattoirs, as compared to 1 herd each by sampling in sow pools and sampling in nucleus and gilt multiplying herds. This, as well as the costs and consequences of positive findings, are important factors to take into account when considering making changes to the *Salmonella* surveillance system for Swedish pigs.

4. Case study 4 – *Echinococcus multilocularis* in Poland

4.1. Assessing the risk profiles of *Echinococcus multilocularis* for 2 different regions, one endemic and one free of disease using active surveillance data from red fox and stray dog populations

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(*Table and figure numbers are consecutive for this case study only)

4.2. Introduction

Alveolar hydatid disease (AHD) is a zoonotic disease caused by larval forms of the tapeworm of the species *Echinococcus multilocularis*. Humans are nonspecific intermediate hosts in the life cycle of this parasite (Karamon *et al.* 2014). *E. multilocularis* produces small cysts spread throughout the internal organs of the infected person and the course of disease depends on the location of the parasite in the human host. The cysts may appear in any organ or tissue, however, 80-95% of them are found in the liver and lungs. As a result of their slow growth, cysts do not initially cause symptoms of the disease and can reach several centimetres in diameter, pushing pressure on the bile ducts to cause cholestasis and the development of jaundice or on the vessels of the hepatic cavity causing hypertension. With pulmonary localization, large cysts appear as coughing, shortness of breath, and/or chest pain. The larvae that develop in the central nervous system and the eyeball are particularly dangerous, where the effect of pressure can cause serious damage to the organs. Predominantly, *E. multilocularis* grows in the liver, penetrating the parenchyma along blood vessels. During the further growth of the larvae, alveoli diameter of 0.5 to 6 mm are formed, which can detach from the cyst and form metastases, moving through the blood vessels and lymph ducts, most often to the lungs and brain. Humans becomes infected accidentally by ingestion of food contaminated with invasive eggs of *E. multilocularis*, which have entered the environment with the faeces of the final hosts. Wild canids, dogs and foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*) act as definitive hosts, harbouring the adult stage of the tapeworm. Ingestion of an intermediate host containing alveolar hydatid cysts by a wild canid can result in an infestation. Eggs of the parasite can be found in faeces, on the hair, mouth and tongue of infected animals, and on contaminated objects. Certain predator species are the final hosts, the most typical of which is the red fox. In Poland, the sources of infection are dogs, foxes and contaminated food. Non-compliance with the rules of hygiene, close contact with infected animals and eating undercooked, unwashed, food contaminated with tapeworm eggs (e.g. vegetables, forest fruits) are risk factors for infection.

4.3. Methods and results

This assessment was based on studies of red foxes hunted during an official anti-rabies vaccination efficacy study in 2009-2013 in 15 provinces in Poland (Karamon *et al.* 2014). The data for the remaining one voivodeship - Lubelskie - came from the years 2007-2008 (Karamon *et al.* 2011). Confidence intervals of 95% were used in all analyses. *E. multilocularis* tapeworms were found in 16.5 (14.7-18.4) % of the examined foxes (255 out of 1546), however, the difference between the regions was highly significant. The areas with a much higher frequency of occurrence were the eastern voivodeships ranging from 17.5 (11.2-26.3) % to 50.0 (40.3-59.7) %, while the western part of the country was characterized by a lower prevalence from 0.0 (0.0-3.7) % to 11.8 (6.9 -19.4) %. The exact values are shown on the map below (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Percentage values of *E. multilocularis* prevalence in foxes in individual Polish voivodeships (provinces) (with 95% confidence intervals). See Table 2 for voivodeship full names.

The cumulative prevalence of the western region of Poland (DS., KP, LB, LD, OP, PM, SL, WP, ZP) was 4.3 (3.1-5.8) %, and the eastern (LU, MP, MZ, PK, PD, SW, WM): 30.1 (27.0-33.3) %. This study clearly indicates the dynamic increase in the incidence of *E. multilocularis* in foxes in the eastern regions of Poland, compared to previous studies. The rapid increase in the percentage of infected foxes began at the turn of the century 20 and 21 (Karamon *et al.* 2011). In the western part of Poland, the percentage of infected foxes was relatively low. In one of the western voivodeships (Opolskie), *E. multilocularis* tapeworms were not detected at all. However, we can't make a statement that it is an *E. multilocularis*-free region since the obtained confidence interval gives a range of 0.0-3.7% for prevalence. In the western part of the country, there was no significant increase in the number of infected foxes - the low incidence in these areas has remained at a similar level for about 15 years (Karamon *et al.* 2014).

The presence of *E. multilocularis* in foxes in the neighbouring countries should be considered in this assessment, however, we cannot claim that this is the main factor contributing to such a clear differentiation of *E. multilocularis* distribution in foxes in Poland. Most cases of AHD were observed in the Warmia-Masuria Province (Nahorski *et al.* 2013), where, according to this study, approximately 50% of foxes were infected. Additionally, detection of the larval form of *E. multilocularis* in the liver of pigs (Karamon *et al.* 2012) emphasizes the danger to humans in Poland. *E. multilocularis* has also been detected in dogs (Karamon *et al.* 2019). Stool samples were collected from 268 dogs in the southern part of the Podkarpackie Province (south-eastern Poland) within the period March 2017 to June 2018. *E. multilocularis* was detected in four dogs 1.5 (0.6-3.8) % - a similar percentage was found in dogs of private owners and from shelters: 1.4 (0.4-4.9) % (2 dogs) and 1.6 (0.5-5.7) % (2 dogs), respectively. Dogs are considered an epidemiologically important member of the *E. multilocularis* life cycle due to their closer relationship to humans than wildlife definitive hosts.

In the process of estimating the risk level, a 6-point scale was used, both in the assessment of the likelihood of occurrence in the animal and the consequence of this occurrence - according to the table below (Table 1).

Table 1. Risk on a qualitative scale as the product of the likelihood and its consequences.

		Consequences					
		Negligible	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high
The likelihood of occurrence in the animal	High	Negligible	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high
	Moderate	Negligible	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high
	Low	Negligible	Negligible	Very low	Low	Moderate	High
	Very low	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Very low	Low	Moderate
	Extremely low	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Very low	Low
	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Very low

In the assessment of the risk profiles for foxes in Poland, the size of the consequences was assumed to be "high". The western and eastern parts of the country should definitely be distinguished in terms of the likelihood of *E. multilocularis* occurrence. With such a division, the risk in the western half of Poland is at the "low" level (the right end of the confidence interval reaches the "moderate" level). The eastern part of Poland is considered as "high" risk (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The risk of *E. multilocularis* in foxes when Poland is divided into two areas - eastern and western.

However, such a division of risk classification could be too generalized as the differences with low prevalence values are quite significant. Hence the following risk characteristics for all voivodships are given separately (Fig. 3), including the extreme values of the confidence intervals of the likelihoods (Table 2).

Fig. 3. The risk of *E. multilocularis* in foxes in all voivodships (provinces) in Poland.

Table 2. The risk of *E. multilocularis* in foxes in all voivodships in Poland with separated values according to the confidence intervals. *Data from the years 2007-2008 (Karamon *et al.* 2011).

Provinces	Risk	95% CI min	95% CI max
Dolnośląskie (DS)	Low	Low	Moderate
Kujawsko-pomorskie (KP)	Low	Low	Moderate
Lubelskie (LU)*	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Lubuskie (LB)	Low	Low	Moderate
Łódzkie (LD)	Moderate	Low	Moderate
Małopolskie (MP)	Moderate	Moderate	High
Mazowieckie (MZ)	High	Moderate	High
Opolskie (OP)	Negligible	Negligible	Low
Podkarpackie (PK)	High	High	High
Podlaskie (PD)	High	Moderate	High
Pomorskie (PM)	Low	Low	Moderate
Śląskie (SL)	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate

Provinces	Risk	95% CI min	95% CI max
Świętokrzyskie (SW)	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Warmińsko-mazurskie (WM)	High	High	High
Wielkopolskie (WP)	Low	Low	Moderate
Zachodniopomorskie (ZP)	Moderate	Low	Moderate

The range of the confidence intervals, due to the size of the sample, does not allow for such a detailed assessment. In turn, assuming the most general, averaged value of the prevalence coefficient for the entire territory of Poland, the obtained risk was "moderate" (including for the entire confidence interval). Regardless of the concept adopted in terms of detail, the entire territory of Poland should rather be treated as an endemic region. Although the discussed studies did not show positive foxes in the Opolskie Voivodeship (OP), it is the smallest voivodeship, surrounded by voivodeships where *E. multilocularis* was invariably detected, and the right end of the confidence interval for the prevalence of OP is 3.7%. At least other similar, several-year-long studies would have to show the absence of tapeworm in this area to be considered a disease-free region.

In the case of dogs, the size of the consequences was rated "very high" due to the close contact of these animals with humans. The risk value is "moderate", based on a recent study of dogs in one of the region's that was most affected by *E. multilocularis* in foxes. And in the case of only stray dogs, the risk is also "moderate", but taking into account the maximum value of the confidence interval of the probability of the event (worst case scenario) we deal with the "high" risk. The level of risk and the dynamic situation observed in the occurrence of this tapeworm support the need for constant monitoring of the presence of *E. multilocularis* in Poland.

5. Case study 5 – *Echinococcus multilocularis* testing in Great Britain

5.1. Cost effectiveness analysis of different diagnostic tests used to demonstrate freedom from disease with reference to *Echinococcus multilocularis* in Great Britain

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(*Table and figure numbers are consecutive for this case study only)

5.2. Introduction

Echinococcus multilocularis is a parasitic tapeworm and causative agent of alveolar echinococcosis in humans (Torgerson *et al.*, 2009). European Union MSs where *E. multilocularis* is not endemic must demonstrate freedom from disease by upholding surveillance in accordance with an output-based scheme prescribed by the European Commission (European Commission, 2017). This requires that MSs demonstrate a prevalence of not more than 1% with a confidence level of at least 95% to be considered free from disease. The UK continues to uphold these standards, despite no longer being an EU MS, and each year submits the outcome of its *E. multilocularis* surveillance to the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH).

The programme in place in the UK features two epidemiological units (Great Britain and Northern Ireland). Foxes are considered to be the definitive wild host, hence, a sample of red foxes are taken randomly and tested each year. The GB fox population is estimated to be between 120,000 and 250,000 (Croft *et al.*, 2017); hence with the current testing methodology, the number of foxes sampled must exceed 383.

Given the costs involved in maintaining this level of surveillance, a detailed economic analysis was carried out to evaluate the current diagnostic test used in the output-based surveillance systems for *E. multilocularis* against alternative tests available. Economic analysis is a broad discipline which evaluates the input cost required to reach a desired output. It is often used to compare the cost and benefit of proposed changes to a system. Economic analysis was reviewed in the One Health EJP project COHESIVE, in the context of controlling food-borne zoonoses. In this, cost-benefit analysis (CBA) was the most common economic analysis method, providing a ratio of the benefit provided by a proposed system against its input costs. Its main advantage is that it uses a wide definition for benefit, encompassing the effects interventions have on less tangible constructs such as human health and wellbeing, and converting these entirely into financial metrics for comparability (Dewar *et al.*, 2021).

However, CBA is fundamentally input-based. It can provide the relationship between societal benefit gained and the input cost of a given testing intensity but focusses less on how a given output can be achieved through these investments. Moreover, both costs and benefits must be in financial terms. Cost effectiveness analysis (CEA) measures the input cost required to produce a given output. Unlike CBA, the 'effectiveness' component of a CEA can be defined by the analyst. For example, some studies use the quality adjusted life year or disability adjusted life year as metrics for effectiveness (Vallejo-Torres *et al.*, 2021, Benedictus *et al.*, 2009, Pitter *et al.*, 2018). However, effectiveness could also be defined as the ability to achieve the target output of an output-based surveillance system.

Here, we apply a CEA to compare the costs of different diagnostic tests in GB against their effectiveness at detecting a 1% prevalence of *E. multilocularis* with 95% confidence.

5.3. Methods

5.3.1.1. Data acquisition

In order to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of each testing methodology proposed, the first step was to investigate what testing methodologies were available for this surveillance. Once this was established, the costs and time involved in carrying out each method needed to be recorded and aggregated.

Stakeholder interviews

Stakeholders were defined as “any parties who are affected by or who can affect the surveillance system” (Friedman *et al.*, 2006). For this study these were considered as:

- Parasitology discipline lead and laboratory coordinator for *E. multilocularis* surveillance in GB.
- Carcass collection coordinator for *E. multilocularis* surveillance in GB.
- Discipline lead for wildlife epidemiology and modelling, leading *E. multilocularis* sample selection, and risk modelling.

These stakeholders provided a range of information on the different tests employed, the processes involved in the current surveillance system, including carcass collections and staff time in the laboratory.

Available tests

Cataloguing the tests available was done through discussions with the stakeholders and through researching the available literature. The annual EFSA report on *E. multilocularis* surveillance in Europe was an essential resource, summarizing how different countries in Europe conducted their tests and describing a range of alternative options (EFSA, 2021). For each test, a range of parameters were assembled, to allow for accurate comparison of their cost-effectiveness. These included the sensitivities of these tests, the consumables and reagents required for each along with the costs for staff time and equipment maintenance.

Three testing types were studied in this assessment:

- The sedimentation and counting technique (SCT) – which is recognized as the gold standard for *E. multilocularis* testing. This involves taking segments from the intestine and washing these with a saline solution, which yields a sediment after several periods of vigorous shaking, removing the supernatant each time. These sediments are then observed under a microscope to count any eggs in the sample (EFSA, 2021).
- The egg flotation (EF) test – used as the primary method of testing for *E. multilocularis* in GB. This involves extracting tissue and faeces from the lower intestine and filtering this with a zinc chloride solution in search of eggs. When found, these are lysed and DNA extracted from these is amplified using polymerase chain reaction (PCR), with fragment sizes measured using gel electrophoresis (Mathis *et al.*, 1996, Dinkel *et al.*, 1998).
- The qPCR test – which is not yet widely used but has been recommended as an alternative to the SCT test. This involves lysis and extraction of *E. multilocularis* DNA from faecal samples, followed by magnetic separation and amplification using real-time PCR (Maksimov *et al.*, 2019).

Costs for each test

The standard operating procedures for each test or methodology described in literature were used to determine what materials, reagents and instruments were required to carry out each test. Stakeholder interviews were used to determine the relative costs of each of these reagents, costings for staff time, sample transport, and post-mortem costs. All cost values were then added together to provide the relative annual costs of maintaining a surveillance system using each test type.

5.3.1.2. Cost effectiveness analysis

CEA measures the calculated input cost to achieve a given outcome. In COHESIVE, CEA of control options for foodborne diseases were reviewed. Effectiveness was determined to be any desired outcome, such as a change in the prevalence of a disease, or a reduction in burden of disease (Dewar *et al.*, 2021). In this case, we define effectiveness as the ability of the surveillance system to conform to the standards set by EFSA and the WOAHA, to detect a prevalence of 1% in the population with 95% confidence.

The total cost over a year applying each testing methodology was converted into an average cost per test. The required testing output of the surveillance system, along with the estimated fox population and test sensitivities was used to calculate the number of samples to be taken from the population. The system was assumed to adopt a simple random testing design. The number of samples to be taken was found using EpiTools, an online sample size calculator developed by AUSVET (AUSVET, 2022). Since positive results were assumed to be followed up and confirmed, the specificity of all tests was set to 1. The minimum number of tests required to demonstrate freedom from disease was then multiplied by the cost per test to provide the overall cost of each testing methodology over one year.

5.3.1.3. Assumptions and limitations

The model has limitations and assumptions based on availability of data and projected vs real information. These are as follows:

1. The economy of scale when testing. Cost per test is calculated based on the size of the complete sample set for the year. We assume that, with the current testing process, the samples will be stored throughout the year and processed in bulk which would allow for greater flexibility and economy in the testing process. If the samples were to be processed in smaller batches as they were received, this would likely result in a greater cost per test than shown by these data.
2. The number of fox carcasses collected is the same as the number sampled or processed. There is likely to be a difference between the two numbers as farmers, game keepers, and hunters often provide more fox carcasses for testing than required (APHA parasitology lead, 2022). This is beneficial to the real testing process as it allows samples to be taken from a more representative spread of animals but may impact the overall cost per test for certain parameters such as consumables and staff time.
3. The costs associated with transport, sample collection, post-mortem, and administrative tasks are the same for each test. These may vary depending on the exact processes, and the number of samples required for each method, but are likely to be similar.
4. There are several variables where exact data could not be found. These were parameterised based on the closest available data.
5. The limitation of this model is that current costs are measured at the time of data collection, without any discounting employed to account for future price trends. If this model were to be used in the future, up-to date values for equipment, maintenance, consumables, transport, and staff time would need to be calculated.
6. The costs considered in this assessment do not include the start-up costs for the various methodologies, such as the costs of new equipment or training.

5.3.1.4. Results

Cost effectiveness calculation

The costs of achieving the target output of the surveillance system were compared between each testing methodology (Table 1). For annualised costs, such as sample collection and post-mortem, the per test

cost was calculated based on the number of samples collected in one sampling year. This was multiplied by the number of tests required, determined using the sensitivities of the tests and the EpiTools calculator.

Table 1, showing the cost-effectiveness of three different testing methodologies for E. multilocularis at detecting a 1% prevalence detection with 95% confidence (values used are proxies to show relative costs).

Parameter	Unit	Test		
		Egg flotation	SCT	qPCR
Species sampled	-	Fox	Fox	Fox
Throughput	-	batch of 20 every 12h	10-20 per day (15)	12-30 min per sample (21)
Test sensitivity	-	0.78	0.78	0.89
Test specificity	-	1	1	1
Consumables and reagents	Per test	£15.20	£1.00	£3.33
Staff time (testing)	Per test	£1.00	£2.47	£1.12
Additional costs (excluding testing)	Annual cost	£100,000.00	£100,000.00	£100,000.00
Equipment	Annual cost	£143	£100	£3017
Tests required at 1% prevalence	No. of tests	383	383	336

The test sensitivity of 0.78 for the EF and SCT methods is the value recommended for use by EFSA for this type of testing, whereas test sensitivity for the qPCR method is the average of those sourced from literature. From these data the qPCR is the most sensitive of the testing methods, reflected in the lower number of tests required per year to demonstrate freedom from disease at 1% prevalence.

Between the three options, the SCT is the most economical when it comes to consumables and reagents, compared to that required for the qPCR and EF respectively. This is also true for the estimated annual cost of equipment and maintenance. This difference is mainly due to the comparatively large maintenance cost for real time PCR equipment. Where these outputs differ, however, is the cost of staff time associated with each test due to the time intensive nature of the SCT (Eckert, 2003).

The additional costs cover all other costs associated with testing such as transport, sample collection, post-mortem, registration, and administrative tasks. These costs could differ slightly both for different testing types, and different years, but any variability is likely relatively low. Therefore, the same baseline value has been used for all testing types in this model.

Overall, in this model the qPCR is shown to be the most cost-effective testing method with the lowest number of tests required per year and consequently the lowest overall cost, despite the higher relative cost of equipment maintenance.

5.3.1.5. Discussion

Overall, the qPCR was found to be the most cost-effective method of routine *E. multilocularis* surveillance in GB among the tests included in this study. The comparatively high test sensitivity means fewer tests are required to meet EFSA's and the WOH's freedom from disease requirements, offsetting the cost of equipment maintenance. The cost of qPCR equipment maintenance could be further justified in a wider laboratory context if this equipment was also used for other testing programmes. The SCT has a range of test sensitivities noted in available literature (Eckert, 2003, Maksimov *et al.*, 2019, Gesy *et al.*, 2013). However, EFSA notes that there is some uncertainty around the actual measured test sensitivity and suggests the estimate of 0.78 is used instead. Should there be additional work in the future that directly measures the sensitivity of the SCT this may affect the outcome of this analysis.

The costs used in this analysis are specific to both the location and date of publication. They are relative proxy costs based on available data and are likely to vary by country and time. This analysis does not account for inflation or other changes to costs over time. However, as inflation will likely affect all test-types evenly, the comparative performance of these methods will remain largely unaffected by this. One aspect not considered in this analysis is the initial investment required to set up the testing. This would cover expenditure such as purchase of equipment, staff training and implementation of a quality assurance scheme. Considering the variability of this initial expenditure, for example cost of different qPCR platforms or choice between internal or external training courses, this was considered out of the scope of this analysis.

Should this work be continued in the future, there would be additional value to performing a cost benefit analysis to look at wider stakeholder perspectives. Particularly, as stakeholders have different priorities it may be beneficial to look at what output is best in the long term for all stakeholders, and whether additional benefits could be gained from testing beyond the minimum legislated requirements.

6. Case study 6 – SARS-CoV-2

6.1. Risk of SARS-COV2 transmission and maintenance at the cat-human interface

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(*Table and figure numbers are consecutive for this case study only)

6.2. Introduction

Continued transmission of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-COV-2) in the human population has generated new virus variants and led to increased numbers of animal species becoming infected with these virus variants. Cats, which are in close contact with humans, have been exposed and infected with SARS-COV-2 since the beginning of the epidemic and observational studies have indicated potential transmission between cats, which has been confirmed experimentally. Furthermore, recent evidence has also highlighted the risk of cat-to-human transmission. Due to the close contact with humans, the role of pets has taken special consideration. Cats have been shown to be particularly susceptible to infection to SARS-COV-2 and able to transmit infection ($R_0 > 1$) to other cats in close contact (Gonzales *et al.*, 2021; Halfmann *et al.*, 2020). However, although cat-to-cat transmission could be sustained ($R_0 > 1$), maintenance of the virus in the cat population will depend on the level of contact between household cats and feral cats as well as the interaction with humans. In addition, circulation of virus in the cat population may lead to generation of new virus variants and/or result in cat-to-human transmission, particularly in conditions similar to those leading to infection of a veterinarian exposed to a sick cat in Thailand (Sila *et al.*, 2022). The objectives of this study were to map the scenarios that would lead to transmission of SARS-COV-2 at the cat-human interface and quantify the probabilities of transmission from humans-to-cats, cats-to-cats and from cats-to-humans.

6.3. Methods

6.3.1.1. Mapping risk pathways for transmission and maintenance of SARS-COV-2 between humans and cats

In order to have a clear overview of the risk of transmission of virus at the human-cat population and the risk of virus maintenance in the cat population we first identified and mapped the possible transmission pathways in the human-cat population. We aimed at identifying pathways and conditions for transmission from human-to-cat (P_{h-c}), from cat-to-cat (P_{c-c}) and from cat-to-human (P_{c-h}).

6.3.1.2. Quantifying probabilities of infection

Following the identification and mapping of the risk pathways we proceeded to quantify the different transmission probabilities from human-to-cat (P_{h-c}), from cat-to-cat (P_{c-c}) and from cat-to-human (P_{c-h}).

Probability of transmission from human-to-cat (P_{h-c})

A systematic literature review was performed to select published literature reporting observational studies on SARS-COV-2 levels of infection in cats. Studies in which the epidemiological units were clearly defined (e.g. household, shelter) were selected for data extraction.

Probability of transmission from cat-to-cat (P_{c-c})

As part of the OH-EJP project COVRIN we performed a systematic literature review to collect data and quantify transmission parameters for cat-to-cat transmission (Gonzales *et al.*, 2021). We used the

between cat R_0 estimates from pair transmission studies to quantify the probability of cat-to-cat transmission as follows:

$$P_{c-c} = \frac{R_0}{R_0+2}$$

Additionally, observational studies were reviewed to collect information on prevalence in shelters and among feral cats, which could be indicators of cat-to-cat transmission.

Probability of transmission from cat-to-human (P_{c-h})

We assumed that transmission from cat-to-human would take place mainly via a human being exposed to virus aerosols (droplets and small particles) exhaled by an infected cat. Hence, we first had to measure the amount of virus exhaled by an infected cat, before we proceeded to quantify P_{c-h}

Quantification of the rate of aerosolized virus exhaled by an infected cat (rVL).

To quantify this rate, we sampled exhaled air from inoculated-infected cats during a challenge experiment assessing susceptibility of cats to infection with SARS-COV-2 (collaboration with project: ARVODI-2018). Breath samples were taken using an AirPort MD8 air sampler (Sartorius) for 3 min at a flow rate of 80 L/min, holding the sampler at the distance of 3 – 5 cm from the cat's nostrils. Aerosol particles are retained on a gelatin filter (nominal pore size 3 μ m) attached to the front of the MD8 sampler, through which air is drawn. The gelatin filter was dissolved in 10 mL PBS after sampling and 1 ml of this dilution was taken for PCR testing and quantification of the rVL (RNA copies) as described elsewhere (Gerhards *et al.*, 2022).

Quantification of P_{c-h}

To quantify this probability (P_{c-h}) we used a deterministic dose response model where:

$$P_{c-h} = 1 - e^{-frD}$$

With f being the fraction of RNA copies expected to be infectious. By multiplying the exhaled RNA-virus loads (rVL) times this fraction we obtain the expected VL in plaque forming units (PFU); r represents the probability that 1 PFU causes infection and D is the total rVL inhaled by a human in close contact (distance < 0.5m) with an infected cat during a determined exposure time t in minutes. Here D is:

$$D = rVL * (m * a) * t$$

where m is the virus inactivation rate (min⁻¹), a is the fraction of exhaled virus by the cat that reaches and is inhaled by the human contact per minute of exposure. For this quantification we assume that human-cat contact takes place a distance < 0.5 meters and in a room with poor or no ventilation. These would represent the worst case scenario. Parameter values are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters used for the quantification of the probability of transmission from cat-to-human

Parameter	Value	Description	Reference
RVh (L/min)	12	Respiratory volume adult human	
RVc (L/min)	0.96	Respiratory volume adult cat	
F	0.013	Fraction of RNA able to infect a cell. Around 80 copies = 1 PFU	Schijven <i>et al.</i> , (2021)

Parameter	Value	Description	Reference
r	0.056	Probability of 1 PFU causing illness	Schijven <i>et al.</i> , (2021)
M	0.008	Virus inactivation rate per min	Schijven <i>et al.</i> , (2021)
	0.1	Aerosol dilution with distance. This is around 0.5 to 1 log for a distance < 0.5 m	Cortellessa <i>et al.</i> , (2021)
rVL (RNA/min)	97.861	Virus load exhaled per minute by an infected cat. Low loads	This study
rVL (RNA/min)	339.318	Virus load exhaled per minute by an infected cat. Average loads	This study
rVL (RNA/min)	6927.994	Virus load exhaled per minute by an infected cat. High loads	This study

6.4. Results

6.4.1.1. Mapping risk pathways for transmission and maintenance of SARS-COV-2 between humans and cats

Figure 1 shows the scenarios that could lead to transmission between humans and cats and among cats at household level and outside the household where pet-cats are likely to contact and infect either pet cats from other households or feral/stray cats.

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Figure 1. Pathways for transmission and maintenance of SARS-COV-2 in the cat population at the human-cat interface.

Probability of transmission from human-to-cat (P_{h-c}).

The probabilities of transmission P_{h-c} can be reflected in the prevalence of infected cats observed in households where the owner was identified infected first. A total of nine studies were selected and data collected. The median reported prevalence (P_{h-c}) of infected cats was 0.2 (range: 0.05 – 0.52). Similarly, the median prevalence of infected cats coming from infected household, detected during a survey in veterinary clinics was 0.15 (Table2).

Table 2 Summary of observational studies assessing prevalence of SARS-COV-2 infection in cats

Epidemiological Unit	Infection status	Number of studies	Total number of cats assessed	Minimum prevalence	Median prevalence	Maximum prevalence
Household	Infected	9	229	0.05	0.2	0.52
Household	Not infected	1	38	0.03	0.03	0.03
Household	Unknown	1	16	0.06	0.06	0.06
Shelter	Unknown	3	455	0.02	0.12	0.23
Vet clinic	Infected	1	13	0.15	0.15	0.15
Vet clinic	Not infected	1	90	0.07	0.07	0.07
Vet clinic	Unknown	7	4293	0	0	1
Feral	Unknown	2	44	0.19	0.21	0.23

Probability of transmission from cat-to-cat (P_{c-c})

Gonzales *et al.*, (2021) reported R_0 estimates for direct contact transmission of 2.3 (95%CI: 1.1 – 4.9). This would result in $P_{c-c} = 0.53$ (0.35 – 0.71). These probabilities are likely to apply to scenarios within a household with more than one cat, where there is intensive and long contact between these animals. Review of literature regarding prevalence of infection in shelters and feral cats reported median prevalence of 0.15 and 0.21 (range: 0.19 – 0.23) respectively (Table 2). These lower probabilities may reflect lower contact frequencies (fewer contacts and/or shorter duration) than contact between cats than cats within a household.

Probability of transmission from cat-to-human (P_{c-h})

We first quantified rVL in experimentally infected cats. Laboratory results are shown in Figure 2. These results which were measured in RNA copies/ml of sample were multiplied by 10 (sample volume) and divided by 2.8 L, which was the total volume of air exhaled by an adult cat during the 3 min of sampling. Conditional on presence of virus aerosols, the average virus exhale rate was $10^{2.5}$ (range: $10^{2.0}$ – $10^{3.8}$) RNA copies/L of air per min (Table 2).

Figure 2. Virus exhaled by infected cats, sampled during a challenge experiment at different days post inoculation (DPI). Three cats were euthanized for pathology studies every three days. Hence not all animals are sampled every DPI shown in the Figure 3, for three scenarios based on low, average or high rVL exhaled by an infected cat.

This rVL was then used to quantify (P_{c-h}) using a deterministic dose-response model. The estimated P_{c-h} as a function of exposure time are presented in Figure 3. The estimates indicate that in a scenario with a cat exhaling high rVL, the probability of transmission to a human is high within a short period of time. We also assessed this probability by increasing α (Aerosol fraction reaching or inhaled by the exposed human) by hundred times (0.01) and the P_{c-h} was higher than 0.5 within 3 minutes of close distance exposure.

Figure 3 Probability of a person becoming infected (P_{c-h}) by close contact (distance < 0.5m) with an infected cat exhaling either low respiratory virus loads (rVL) ($10^{1.45}$ copies/min) (dashed line), moderate rVL ($10^{1.9}$ copies/min) (light gray line) or high rVL ($10^{3.3}$ copies/min) (dark line). It was assumed that a person would inhale (be directly exposed to) around 1/10 of the rVL exhaled by the cat.

6.5. Conclusions

In this study, transmission pathways at the human-cat interface have been mapped and the probabilities of transmission within these pathways quantified. These estimates appear to indicate that close interaction between cats and humans and probable transmission from humans-to-cats and then between cats may ensure maintenance of SARS-COV-2 in the cat population, with the highest risk of virus introduction in cats coming from infected humans. Whilst transmission between cats is probable, the probability of transmission depends on the degree of between cat contact. $P_{c-c} > 0.3$ ($R_0 > 1$) may be probable between cats in close contact for long periods. The latter could be observed for cats in the same household or sharing the same cage in a shelter for a couple of days. Lower contact intensity between cats outside the household (pet and feral cats) may lead to lower probabilities of cat-to-cat transmission ($P_{c-c} \leq 0.23$). However, observed probabilities appear to indicate that this risk, although apparently low, is higher than negligible. Reports of infected cats detected in households with negative owners (Table 2), provide further confirmation that cats have likely been exposed outside the household and contracted infection by exposure to a contaminated environment (Gerhards *et al.*, 2022; Oreshkova *et al.*, 2020) or contact with an infected cat.

The analysis appears to indicate that transmission from cat-to-human is probable, particularly in scenarios where a human is in contact with a cat exhaling high virus loads. In this scenario, a high probability of infection (transmission to) of the exposed human is expected, after a few minutes

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exposure. This would reflect the case reported by Sila *et al.*, (2022), where a veterinarian was exposed to an infected cat probably shedding very high virus loads (throat swabs Ct values 17 (ORF1 gene) and 16 (N gene) (Sila *et al.*, 2022). However, it is difficult to quantify how often such a scenario would take place, since the frequency of cats exhaling high levels of virus may be low. When a human is exposed to cats shedding average to low rVL, the risk of transmission will depend on the duration of the contact. Owners' behavior, such as sharing bed with pets; exposes the pets or the person to a high risk of transmission from either the owner-to-cat or from the cat-to-owner.

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7. Discussion

Output based standards can allow for variation in surveillance activities to achieve the same objective and may be useful in the OH context where surveillance for animal pathogens can act as risk indicators for human health. The flexibility which using OBS allows, however, also requires more transparency to assist stakeholders, trade partners, decision-makers and risk assessors in interpreting the validity of the surveillance outcomes (Comin *et al.*, 2019). The case studies used in this report describe aspects of methodology that can contribute to achieving an OBS and which can be used to demonstrate the validity of using an OBS. Three of the case studies for this deliverable used *Salmonella* spp. (a MATRIX Hazard Track), as the target pathogens, which are endemic in the relevant animal sectors. The methodologies demonstrate evidence of case finding capacity of different surveillance components (Case study 3), different sampling strategies (Case study 2) and a proposed modelling framework incorporating relevant risk factors (Case study 1). All of these factors need to be considered when proposing an OBS and the surveillance strategies that need to be employed to achieve it. The example of *E. multilocularis* (a MATRIX Emerging Threat Hazard Track) in Poland (Case study 4) concentrates on risk levels of red fox populations in different areas which should be considered when designing a surveillance method to achieve confidence in a specific OBS. Several European countries are considered free of *E. multilocularis* and already use OBS to demonstrate freedom from disease (EFSA 2021). Case study 5 uses this example to demonstrate a cost effectiveness analysis of the different diagnostic tests available for use in such a surveillance scheme in GB. Historical data is useful when using any system to generate an OBS as it proves the length of time over which disease has been absent (freedom from disease) or chronological detection for endemic diseases. The final case study (Case study 6) maps the risk pathways leading to transmission of SARS-CoV-2 (a MATRIX Emerging Threat Hazard Track) between human-cat populations. Mapping such pathways is important especially with emerging pathogens as risk factors for infection can influence the surveillance methodology used.

Key to the effectiveness of any surveillance system is the selection of appropriate methodologies to achieve the objectives of the system whether it be increasing efficiency, introducing mitigations or changing the surveillance components. A robust methodology which can evaluate the different aspects of surveillance and demonstrate confidence in the OBS is essential for stakeholder engagement and the case studies shown here help illustrate how these methodologies can be approached. With regards to a OH approach it has been shown that National Control Programmes for *Salmonella* have correlated with a decline in human cases of human salmonellosis in several EU countries (Korsgaard *et al.*, 2009; Tzani *et al.*, 2021). There are a number of critical points where surveillance for *Salmonella* can be carried out e.g. on farm, at the slaughterhouse, at the supermarket etc. There is likely to be a different purpose and different stakeholders for each scheme (Korsgaard *et al.*, 2009), but utilizing an OBS at the animal surveillance level for some pathogens may have benefits from a OH approach as has already been demonstrated.

This deliverable has showcased different methodologies used by MATRIX partners to achieve an OBS using a variety of surveillance activities. Most surveillance, control and monitoring programmes still rely on input-based standards but demonstrating statistically based confidence in an OBS can allow for more flexibility and cost efficiency. The second deliverable of WP3 (due October 2022) will consist of non-prescriptive guidelines for conducting output-based surveillance regarding current practice, stakeholder engagement and evaluation strategies.

8. References

- Ågren E.C.C, Stermberg Lewerin S, Frössling J. 2018. Evaluation of herd-level sampling strategies for control of Salmonella in Swedish cattle. *J Dairy Sci.* 101:10177-10190. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2018-14786>
- Arnold ME, Carrique-Mas JJ, Davies RH. Sensitivity of environmental sampling methods for detecting Salmonella Enteritidis in commercial laying flocks relative to the within-flock prevalence. *Epidemiol Infect.* 2010;138(3):330-9
- Arnold ME, Carrique-Mas JJ, McLaren I, Davies RH. A comparison of pooled and individual bird sampling for detection of Salmonella in commercial egg laying flocks. *Prev Vet Med.* 2011;99(2-4):176-84
- Arnold ME, Martelli F, McLaren I, Davies RH. Estimation of the sensitivity of environmental sampling for detection of Salmonella in commercial layer flocks post-introduction of national control programmes. *Epidemiol Infect.* 2014;142(5):1061-9.
- AUSVET. 2022. *Sample size to achieve specified population level (or herd, flock, cluster, etc) sensitivity* [Online]. AUSVET. Available: <https://epitools.ausvet.com.au/freedomss> [Accessed 23/05/2022].
- Benedictus, A., Hogeveen, H. & Berends, B. 2009. The price of the precautionary principle: Cost-effectiveness of BSE intervention strategies in the Netherlands. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 89, 212-222.
- Bordier M, Uea-Anuwong T, Binot A, Hendriks P, Goutard FL. Characteristics of One Health surveillance systems: A systematic literature review. *Prev Vet Med.* 2020 Aug;181:104560. doi: 10.1016/j.prevetmed.2018.10.005. Epub 2018 Oct 13. PMID: 30528937.
- Cameron AR. The consequences of risk-based surveillance: Developing output-based standards for surveillance to demonstrate freedom from disease. *Prev Vet Med.* 2012;105(4):280-6. issn: 1873-1716. doi: 10.1016/j.prevetmed.2012.01.009.
- Carrique-Mas JJ, Breslin M, Sayers AR, McLaren I, Arnold M, Davies R. Comparison of environmental sampling methods for detecting Salmonella in commercial laying flocks in the UK. *Lett Appl Microbiol.* 2008a;47(6):514-9
- Carrique-Mas JJ, Breslin M, Snow L, Arnold ME, Wales A, McLaren I, et al. Observations related to the Salmonella EU layer baseline survey in the United Kingdom: follow-up of positive flocks and sensitivity issues. *Epidemiol Infect.* 2008b;136(11):1537-46.
- Comin A, Grewar J, Schaik Gv, Schwermer H, Paré J, El Allaki F, Drewe JA, Lopes Antunes AC, Estberg L, Horan M, Calvo-Artavia FF, Jibril AH, Martínez-Avilés M, Van der Stede Y, Antoniou S-E and Lindberg A (2019) Development of Reporting Guidelines for Animal Health Surveillance—AHSURED. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 6:426. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2019.00426
- Cortellessa, G., Stabilea, L., Arpino, F., Faleiros, D.E., van den Bos, W., Morawskac, L., Buonanno, G., 2021. Close proximity risk assessment for SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Science of the Total Environment* 794 148749.

Croft, S., Chauvenet, A. L. & Smith, G. C. 2017. A systematic approach to estimate the distribution and total abundance of British mammals. *PLoS one*, 12, e0176339.

Dewar, R., Grace, K., Conrady, B., Kaesbohrer, A., Simons, R. & McCarthy, C. 2021. DeliverableD-JIP2-3.8.0: Review of Economic Analyses Conducted on Foodborne Zoonoses. Zenodo: Animal and Plant Health Agency, One Health EJP

Dinkel, A., Von Nickisch-Rosenegk, M., Bilger, B., Merli, M., Lucius, R. & Romig, T. 1998. Detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in the definitive host: coprodiagnosis by PCR as an alternative to necropsy. *Journal of clinical microbiology*, 36, 1871-1876.

Drewe, J., Hoinville, L., Cook, A., Floyd, T., & Stark, K. (2012). Evaluation of animal and public health surveillance systems: A systematic review. *Epidemiology and Infection*, 140(4), 575-590. doi:10.1017/S0950268811002160

Dupuy C, Hendrikx P, Hardstaff J, Lindberg A. Contribution of meat inspection to animal health surveillance in bovine animals. Supporting publications 2012:EN-322. [53 pp.]. Available online: www.efsa.europa.eu/publications

Eckert, J. 2003. Predictive values and quality control of techniques for the diagnosis of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in definitive hosts. *Acta Tropica*, 85, 157-163.

European Commission 2017. COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) 2018/772. In: EUROPEAN UNION (ed.) 2018/772. Brussels: EUR-LEX.

EFSA. Report of the Task Force on Zoonoses Data Collection on the Analysis of the baseline study on the prevalence of *Salmonella* in holdings of laying hen flocks of *Gallus gallus*. *EFSA Journal*. 2007;97

EFSA, 2008. Report of the task force on zoonoses data collection on the analysis of the baseline survey on the prevalence of *Salmonella* in slaughter pigs in the EU, 2006-2007, Part A: *Salmonella* prevalence estimates, *EFSA Journal* 2008; 135, 1-111. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2008.135r>

EFSA, 2009. Analysis of the baseline survey on the prevalence of *Salmonella* in holdings with breeding pigs, in the EU, 2008, Part A: *Salmonella* prevalence estimates, *EFSA Journal* 2009; 7(12):[93 pp]. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2009.1377>

EFSA/ECDC. The European Union One Health 2018 Zoonoses Report. *EFSA Journal* 2019;17:5926.

EFSA and ECDC (European Food Safety Authority and European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control), 2021. The European Union One Health 2020 Zoonoses Report. *EFSA Journal* 2021;19(12):6971, 324 pp. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2021.6971>

EFSA (European Food Safety Authority) and Zancanaro G, 2021. Annual assessment of *Echinococcus multilocularis* surveillance reports submitted in 2021 in the context of Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/772. *EFSA Journal* 2021;19(11):6945, 57 pp. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2021.6945> ISSN:1831-4732©2021

Friedman, A. L., & Miles, S. (2006). *Stakeholders: Theory and practice*. OUP Oxford.

Gerhards, N.M., Gonzales, J.L., Vreman, S., Ravesloot, L., van den Brand, J.M.A., Doekes, H.P., Egberink, H.F., Stegeman, A., Oreshkova, N., van der Poel, W.H.M., de Jong, M.C.M., 2022. Efficient

direct and limited environmental transmission of SARS-CoV-2 lineage B.1.22 in domestic cats. bioRxiv, 2022.2006.2017.496600.

Gesy, K., Pawlik, M., Kapronczai, L., Wagner, B., Elkin, B., Schwantje, H. & Jenkins, E. 2013. An improved method for the extraction and quantification of adult *Echinococcus* from wildlife definitive hosts. *Parasitology Research*, 112, 2075-2078.

Gonzales, J.L., de Jong, M.C.M., Gerhards, N.M., Van der Poel, W.H.M., 2021. The SARS-CoV-2 Reproduction Number R0 in Cats. *Viruses* 13, 2480.

Halfmann, P.J., Hatta, M., Chiba, S., Maemura, T., Fan, S., Takeda, M., Kinoshita, N., Hattori, S.I., SakaiTagawa, Y., Iwatsuki-Horimoto, K., Imai, M., Kawaoka, Y., 2020. Transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in Domestic Cats. *N Engl J Med*.

Helms M, Vastrup P, Gerner-Smidt P, Mølbak K. Short and long term mortality associated with foodborne bacterial gastrointestinal infections: registry based study. *BMJ*. 2003 Feb 15;326(7385):357. PMID: 12586666; PMCID: PMC148890.

Henderson, K. & Mason, C. (2017) Diagnosis and control of *Salmonella* Dublin in dairy herds. In *Practice*39, 158-168

Houe H, Nielsen SS, Nielsen LR, Ethelberg S and Mølbak K (2019) Opportunities for Improved Disease Surveillance and Control by Use of Integrated Data on Animal and Human Health. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 6:301. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2019.00301

Jordbruksverket, 2007. Översyn av salmonellakontrollprogrammet. Jordbruksverket rapport 2007:10. Available online: Översyn av salmonellakontrollprogrammet - Jordbruksverket

Karamon J, Sroka J, Cencek T, Michalski MM, Zięba P, Karwacki J (2011) Prevalence of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in red foxes in two eastern provinces of Poland. *Bull Vet Inst Pulawy* 55: 429–433

Karamon J, Sroka J, Cencek T (2012) The first detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in slaughtered pigs in Poland. *Vet Parasitol* 185: 327–329

Karamon J, Kochanowski M, Sroka J, Cencek T, Różycki M, Chmurzyńska E, Bilaska-Zajęc E (2014) The prevalence of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in red foxes in Poland—current results (2009–2013). *Parasitol Res* 113: 317–322

Karamon J, Kochanowski M, Dąbrowska J, Różycki M, Bilaska-Zajęc E, Sroka J, Cencek T (2015) *Echinococcus multilocularis* w Polsce – sytuacja epizootyczna u lisów wskaźnikiem ryzyka zarażenia ludzi. *Życie Weterynaryjne* 90(9): 580–584

Karamon J, Sroka J, Dąbrowska J, Bilaska-Zajęc E, Zdybel J, Kochanowski M, Różycki M, Cencek T (2019) First report of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in cats in Poland: a monitoring study in cats and dogs from a rural area and animal shelter in a highly endemic region. *Parasites Vectors* 12: 313

Korsgaard H, Madsen M, Feld NC, Mygind J, Hald T. The effects, costs and benefits of *Salmonella* control in the Danish table-egg sector. *Epidemiol Infect.* 2009 Jun;137(6):828-36. doi: 10.1017/S0950268808000903. Epub 2008 Jul 22. PMID: 18644168.

Lester, A., Bruun, B. G., Husum, P., Kolmos, H. J., Nielsen, B. B., Scheibel, J. H. Et al., (1995) Salmonella Dublin. Ugeskr Loeger157, 20-24

Lombard JE, Beam AL, Nifong EM, Fossler CP, Koprak CA, Dargatz DA, Wagner BA, Erdman MM, Fedorka-Cray PJ. 2012. Comparison of individual, pooled, and composite fecal sampling methods for detection of Salmonella on U.S. dairy operations. J Food Prot. 75(9):1562-1571. <https://doi.org/10.4315/0362-028X.JFP-12-012>

Małacka I, Bąbłowica – Echinokokoza. Wojewódzka Stacja Sanitarno-Epidemiologiczna w Poznaniu <https://www.gov.pl/web/wsse-poznan/bablowica---echinokokoza>

Maksimov, P., Isaksson, M., Schares, G., Romig, T. & Conraths, F. 2019. Validation of PCR-based protocols for the detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* DNA in the final host using the Intestinal Scraping Technique as a reference. *Food and Waterborne Parasitology*, 15, e00044.

Martin PA, Cameron AR, Greiner M. 2007. Demonstrating freedom from disease using multiple complex data sources: 1: A new methodology based on scenario trees. *Prev Vet Med*, May 16;79(2-4):71-97.

Mathis, A., Deplazes, P. & Eckert, J. 1996. An improved test system for PCR-based specific detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* eggs. *Journal of helminthology*, 70, 219-222.

Meletis, E. Conrady, B. Hopp, P. Lurier, T. Frössling, J. Rosendal, T. Faverjon, C. Carmo, L. P. Hodnik, J. J. Ózsvári, L. Kostoulas, P. van Schaik, G. Nielen, M. Knific, T. Schulz, J. Šerić-Haračić, S. Madouasse, A. Output-based methodological approaches for substantiating freedom from infection (Manuscript currently under review) <https://sound-control.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Deliverable-3.1.-Output-based-methodological-approaches-for-substantiating-freedom-from-infection.pdf>

Mercat et al., 2022: Capacity of a Bayesian model to detect infected herds using disease dynamics and risk factor information from surveillance programmes: A simulation study.

Madouasse et al., 2021: A modelling framework for the prediction of the herd-level probability of infection from longitudinal data. *PCI Animal Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.07.10.197426>

Nahorski WL, Knap JP, Pawłowski ZS, Krawczyk M, Polański J, Stefaniak J, Patkowski W, Szostakowska B, Pietkiewicz H, Grzeszczuk A, Felczak-Korzybska I, Gołąb E, Wnukowska N, Paul M, Kacprzak E, Sokolewicz-Bobrowska E, Niścigorska-Olsen J, Czyrznikowska A, Chomicz L, Cielecka D, Myjak P (2013) Human alveolar echinococcosis in Poland: 1990–2011. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis* 7(1):e1986. doi:10.1371/journal.pntd.0001986

National Veterinary Institute, 2021. Surveillance of infectious diseases in animals and humans in Sweden 2020. National Veterinary Institute (SVA), Uppsala, Sweden. SVA:s rapportserie 68 1654-7098. Available online: Surveillance of infectious diseases in animals and humans in Sweden 2020 - SVA

Nielsen, 2013: Salmonella Dublin in cattle epidemiology, design and evaluation of surveillance and eradication programmes. Available at: https://static-curis.ku.dk/portal/files/168826927/Liza_Rosenbaum_Nielsen_DrVetSci_dissertation_090813.pdf

Nielsen, 2021: The Danish approach to control of salmonella in cattle. Presentation 2nd of November 2021: Danida Fellowship Center course 2021 Food Safety in the Dairy Sector.

Oreshkova, N., Molenaar, R.J., Vreman, S., Harders, F., Oude Munnink, B.B., Hakze-van der Honing, R.W., Gerhards, N., Tolsma, P., Bouwstra, R., Sikkema, R.S., Tacken, M.G., de Rooij, M.M., Weesendorp, E., Engelsma, M.Y., Brusckke, C.J., Smit, L.A., Koopmans, M., van der Poel, W.H., Stegeman, A., 2020. SARS-CoV-2 infection in farmed minks, the Netherlands, April and May 2020. *Euro Surveill* 25.

Peyre M, Hoinville L, Njoroge J, Cameron A, Traon D, Goutard F, et al. The RISKSUR EVA tool (Survtool): A tool for the integrated evaluation of animal health surveillance systems. *Prev Vet Med.* 2019;173:104777.

Pitter JG, Vokó Z, Józwiak Á, Berkics A. Campylobacter control measures in indoor broiler chicken: critical re-assessment of cost-utility and putative barriers to implementation. *Epidemiol Infect.* 2018 Aug;146(11):1433-1444. doi: 10.1017/S0950268818001528. Epub 2018 Jun 27. PMID: 29945691; PMCID: PMC9133679.

Schijven, J., Vermeulen, L.C., Swart, A., Meijer, A., Duizer, E., de Roda Husman, A.M., 2021. Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment for Airborne Transmission of SARS-CoV-2 via Breathing, Speaking, Singing, Coughing, and Sneezing. *Environmental Health Perspectives* 129, 1 -10.

SEGES, 2022: Salmonella Dublin. Available at: https://www.landbrugsinfo.dk/public/f/c/9/salmonella_dublin_kvag

Sila, T., Sunghan, J., Laochareonsuk, W., Surasombatpattana, S., Kongkamol, C., Ingviya, T., Siripaitoon, P., Kositpantawong, N., Kanchanasuwan, S., Hortiwakul, T., Charernmak, B., Nwabor, O.F., Silpapojakul, K., Chusri, S., 2022. Suspected Cat-to-Human Transmission of SARS-CoV-2, Thailand, July-September 2021. *Emerg Infect Dis* 28, 1485-1488

SSI, 2022:
<https://statistik.ssi.dk/sygdomsdata#!/?sygdomskode=SALM&stype=9&xaxis=Aar&show=Graph&datatype=Laboratory>

Torgerson, P. & Craig, P. 2009. Risk assessment of importation of dogs infected with *Echinococcus multilocularis* into the UK. *Veterinary Record*, 165, 366-368.

Tzani M, Mandilara G, Dias JG, Sideroglou T, Chrysostomou A, Mellou K. Impact of Salmonella Control Programmes in Poultry on Human Salmonellosis Burden in Greece. *Antibiotics (Basel)*. 2021 Jan 28;10(2):121. doi: 10.3390/antibiotics10020121. PMID: 33525354; PMCID: PMC7912426.

Vallejo-Torres L, Rivero-Santana A, Martín-Saborido C, Epstein D, Perestelo-Pérez L, Castellano-Fuentes CL, Escobar-Martínez A, Serrano-Aguilar P. Cost-effectiveness analysis of a surveillance program to prevent hip dislocation in children with cerebral palsy. *Gac Sanit.* 2020 Jul-Aug;34(4):377-384. doi: 10.1016/j.gaceta.2019.05.005. Epub 2019 Sep 15. PMID: 31530485.

Warnick et al., 2006: Simulation model estimates of test accuracy and predictive values for the Danish Salmonella surveillance program in dairy herds. *Prev. Vet. Med.* doi: 10.1016/j.prevetmed.2006.08.001

WOAH Animal Health Surveillance. Terrestrial Animal Health Code (2019). 2019 Chapter 14.

Zoonosynk, 2014. MSB project: Sektorsövergripande förmågebedömning av övervakningssystem för sex viktiga zoonoser, SVA Dnr 2014/734.